

PRO-SIS

Sviluppo e disseminazione di algoritmi per il progetto delle innovative strategie di protezione sismica "CONSTRAIN" e applicazione pilota su edifici esistenti in muratura

Razvoj in diseminacija postopkov za projektiranje inovativnega načina potresnega utrjevanja obstoječih zidanih stavb "CONSTRAIN"

Report 2.4
Linee guida per la
progettazione e
applicazione delle strategie
"CONSTRAIN"

NOVEMBRE 2025

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vgradnjo potresnih utrditev iz
projekta "CONSTRAIN"

NOVEMBER 2025

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PRO-SIS

Development and dissemination of procedures for designing an innovative way seismic strengthening of existing masonry buildings "CONSTRAIN"

Report 2.4 Guidelines for the design and implementation of the "CONSTRAIN" strategies

NOVEMBER 2025

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Report 2.4

Guidelines for the design and implementation of the “CONSTRAIN” strategies

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ANNEX A - Example of price analyses

1. INTRODUCCION

The report collects the results of Activity 2.4 of the PRO-SIS project, aimed at the Preparation of guidelines for the effective design and implementation of the intervention strategies developed within the “CONSTRAIN” project.

Within the CONSTRAIN project (INTERREG V-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2014-2020 - <https://2014-2020.ita-slo.eu/it/constrain>), strategies to reduce the seismic vulnerability of existing masonry were developed and tested in an extensive experimental campaign. The strengthening method developed is based on the use of mortar coatings reinforced with fibre-based composite materials. The main advantage of this system is that it can be applied to only one side of the wall, making it much more convenient for residents and businesses. As construction work can be carried out only on the exterior of the building, people and their belongings do not have to be relocated, and business activity does not have to be interrupted. Furthermore, valuable artistic decorations can be preserved on the interior (or exterior, when interior application is preferred). The strengthening method stands out due to its proven effectiveness in tests on structural components and a full-scale pilot building.

The aim of the “PRO-SIS” project (INTERREG VI-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2021-2027 - <https://www.ita-slo.eu/it/pro-sis>) is to develop the necessary methods for designing and applying these strategies. To this end, the design procedures have been developed based on analytical and numerical analyses calibrated against the experimental results of “CONSTRAIN”. The results provide designers with robust strategies for designing the proposed systems, as well as instructions for design in commonly used commercial structural design programmes.

This document presents the guidelines for the use, design, installation, and maintenance of the CONSTRAIN strengthening method. The document is divided into sections according to the reader's interests:

- In the section for *owners and investors*, there is information about when strengthening is required, when it is sensible to use CONSTRAIN strengthening, the financial aspects, and how it can be applied to structures with elements of cultural heritage.
- The section for *designers* describes all steps of the design process. The description begins with inspection of the structure before strengthening and continues with recommendations for acquiring data for design. The process of modelling structures to assess seismic resistance is presented from the perspective of individual components and the structure as a whole. Examples of analyses and instructions on interpreting results obtained from different commercial software are provided. Finally, the maintenance manual for the CRM is presented.
- The final segment is intended for *builders* and contains detailed instructions for all steps of the application, beginning with the inspection of the wall, followed by preparation for the application of CONSTRAIN strengthening, and the strengthening process itself. Each step is described in detail and accompanied by illustrative diagrams or photographs. Key steps and possible errors are also presented.

2. INFORMATION FOR HOME OWNERS AND INVESTORS

2.1. When and why is it necessary to strengthen existing masonry structures?

Existing masonry buildings were mostly built in the past, when there were no building regulations or when the design loads for structures were much lower than they are today. Furthermore, it was not known which areas were prone to earthquakes and which were considered safe. The Balkans and the Italian peninsula are two of the most seismically active regions in Europe (Fig. 2.1). Historic masonry structures generally do not have problems under regular use or even wind loads, and masonry structures can be extremely durable. However, earthquake loads are very dangerous, as after each major earthquake a large proportion of damage occurs specifically in old masonry buildings, as illustrated in Fig. 2.2. Such structures are therefore inevitably at higher risk than those built after the introduction of modern, systematic construction regulations, which began around the 1980s in both Slovenia and Italy. Unlike old masonry construction, modern earthquake-resistant masonry is built using confined masonry technology with reinforced concrete ties and reinforced concrete floors, and is quite safe in the event of an earthquake.

Fig. 2.1 Extract of a map of earthquake hazard (<http://www.efehr.org/earthquake-hazard/hazard-map/>).

There are *several key vulnerabilities in historic masonry* buildings.

Firstly, the walls and floors are often not properly connected (tied), which can lead to a loss of structural integrity during an earthquake. If a structure loses integrity, it no longer distributes seismic loads among all the load-bearing walls; instead, each wall or part of the structure responds individually. Such a structure is much weaker, as it fails as soon as its weakest part fails. In contrast, a well-connected structure can distribute loads from damaged parts to undamaged parts, making it much more resilient. Therefore, one of the first steps in retrofitting historic structures is to tie the walls and floors using ties and to strengthen weak wooden floors.

Once structural integrity is achieved, the walls are strengthened, which can be done in various ways depending on the characteristics of the masonry. This is necessary to improve the strength of the masonry material, as historic masonry is often quite weak in shear and bending

– loads that occur during earthquakes. It should be noted that there is considerable variability in the strength of masonry. Regular masonry built with good mortar is significantly stronger than loose masonry built from rubble or pebble stones with poor mortar. The need for strengthening therefore depends on the quality of the existing masonry, as well as the seismic hazard and soil conditions at the location.

For a masonry building to respond well to seismic loads, it must also be regular in plan and height. Regularity implies forms that are close to symmetric, with a sufficient number of walls in both directions (e.g. east-west and south-north), similarly sized rooms, and minimal change from floor to floor. Deviations from regularity increase the seismic vulnerability of the structure.

Finally, masonry structures are highly sensitive to any uneven settlement of the foundations. The quality of the foundations and the soil conditions beneath the structure are therefore critical.

Fig. 2.2 The village of Pescara del Tronto- AP (a) before and (b) after the Central Italy earthquake in 2016. The building in the front was obviously heavily damaged, but the village in the back was also severely affected. The village was hit so hard because the construction quality was exceptionally bad in this poor, rural area. The building is also on a steep slope, with many landslides causing further damage.

Although old masonry buildings are not as safe as modern ones, the codes do not require owners to upgrade them unless there is an intervention in the load-bearing structure. Unfortunately, almost all adaptations in old masonry buildings aim to improve comfort and functionality, which often involves removing parts of walls or enlarging openings. In other words, the existing structure is weakened. Even removing partition walls is problematic, as partition walls in existing masonry buildings often form part of the load-bearing structure. Therefore, seismic resistance should be assessed before any intervention. Even when the load-bearing structure is not affected, such as when adding thermal insulation to the façade, it is sensible to consider the seismic resistance of the building. Once a new façade is installed, opportunities for strengthening are greatly reduced. In summary, *the seismic resistance of existing masonry buildings should always be considered* when planning any major interventions to the property.

In practice, interventions in the load-bearing structure are often carried out without considering the seismic response of the entire building. Removing a wall, or even just cutting openings in a wall to increase living space in one apartment of a multistorey apartment building, not only weakens the building but also creates asymmetry in the floor plan and elevation. These effects reduce seismic resistance far more than the size of the removed wall would suggest. Furthermore, the gravity loads previously carried by the removed wall still need to be transferred to the foundations, which increases the loads on adjacent walls, increases floor deflection, and may cause cracking in the structure. Because of such effects, *professional structural engineers should be consulted before any intervention.*

A proper estimation of the effect on the load-bearing structure includes a survey of the entire structure, a numerical analysis of the structure in its existing state, and an analysis after the planned intervention. As a rule, such analysis for existing masonry structures in areas with seismic risk will show insufficient seismic resistance. *A high-quality structural engineering project therefore always includes a plan for seismic strengthening of the structure.*

2.2. What is CRM and seismic strengthening CONSTRAIN?

The acronym CRM stands for Composite Reinforced Mortar. CRM strengthening consists of a 3 cm thick layer of mortar (referred to as coating) applied to the surface of the wall, reinforced with fibre-based composite materials (Fig. 2.3). Currently, the most commonly used materials are hydraulic lime mortar and Glass Fibre-Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) meshes for reinforcement, but mixed lime-cement mortar and other types of fibrous materials may also be used. The coating can be applied to one or both sides of the wall and must be anchored to the wall using various types of anchors.

Fig. 2.3 Example of a CRM system during installation.

The CONSTRAIN seismic strengthening is a CRM consisting of a hydraulic lime coating, reinforced with GFRP meshes and connected to the masonry by special anchors. The system is shown schematically in the images below (Fig. 2.4-Fig. 2.5).

The coating can be applied to both sides of the wall, which is structurally preferable (the strengthening is symmetrical, the masonry is well confined, and the mechanical benefits are greater). Alternatively, the coating can be applied to only one side (for example, the outer side, which reduces inconvenience for residents or businesses). Different types of anchors are used depending on the type of masonry and the number of sides being strengthened. For CRM applied to both sides, pairs of GFRP L-shaped connectors, overlapping in the middle of the wall, can be used (Fig. 2.4a and Fig. 2.5a). Similarly, for single leaf walls, simple GFRP L-shaped connectors can be applied (Fig. 2.5b). The connectors are always fixed with structural adhesives (injections) to ensure sufficient connection to the wall. In the case of multiple leaf walls with the CRM applied on one side, on the other hand, the GFRP L-shaped connectors should be combined with special artificial diatons (Fig. 2.4b and Fig. 2.5c). The diatons consist of concrete cores with an embedded threaded steel bar to connect the usually poorly connected leaves and provide additional confining action. The benefit of the CONSTRAIN technology is that it is thoroughly tested and reliable, even when applied to only one side of the wall.

Fig. 2.4 CONSTRAN strengthening of stone masonry walls: strengthening on both sides (a), and on only one side (b)

Fig. 2.5 CONSTRAN strengthening of brick masonry walls: strengthening on both sides (a), and on only one side, in the case of single (b) or multiple (c) leaf wall.

2.3. In what cases is the use of CRM strengthening sensible?

The use of CRM is a sensible solution for the structural strengthening of masonry when it is necessary to increase the mechanical properties of the walls, which leads to an improvement in the building's overall response to earthquake loads (prevents damage as shown in Fig. 2.6a). CRM strengthening is also very effective at preventing local failure mechanisms (prevents damage as shown in Fig. 2.6b). It is also sensible to use on multi-leaf masonry (Fig. 2.6c-d), as the transversal connector system included in the CRM technique connects the leaves, making them monolithic. Moreover, CRM provides a tying effect (Fig. 2.6d,e), connecting the walls and floors into a mutually reinforcing structurally connected system. This gives the structures the much-desired box-like behaviour, and makes them capable of withstanding earthquakes of higher intensity.

CRM can also be useful for repairing and preventing the degradation and disintegration of masonry: the reinforced layer fills any voids, homogenises the structure, and provides protection against further degradation.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Fig. 2.6: Typical cases suitable for CRM strengthening: (a) prevention of global earthquake damage, (b) prevention of local out-of-plane mechanisms, (c) improving multi leaf walls, (d, e) tying of walls into box-like structure.

2.4. Pros and cons of CRM

Although the CRM strengthening system offers many benefits, it is not always the optimal choice. The decision regarding its use should be based on a holistic assessment by all parties involved (investor, residents, civil engineer, cultural heritage supervisor, etc.), always taking into account the specific characteristics of the structure.

PROs:

CRM can provide *significant benefits to the seismic performance* of masonry walls, in terms of resistance, deformation, and dissipation capacities, both in the case of in-plane and out-of-plane actions.

Composite fibre-based reinforcement is preferred over steel because of its *lower risk of corrosion, reduced coating thickness, and greater durability*.

CRM strengthening is based on lime-based mortars (inorganic matrix), which are *mechanically and chemically more compatible with masonry* than epoxy glue (organic matrix) or high-performance cement-based mortars, which are typically characterised by high stiffness and reduced breathability.

The small thickness of the mortar causes a *very small increase in mass and stiffness*.

From the perspective of the Heritage Conservation Service, which is often relevant for historic masonry structures, CRM is a better solution than, for example, grouting, because it *has a lower impact on the building elements* (see §2.5). In particular, the CRM coatings are *almost entirely removable* which means that returning the structure to its original state is possible.

The application of the CRM application *is relatively easy and clean*. Composite meshes, typically supplied in rolls, are lightweight and easy to transport within the building, as well as easy to cut to the optimal size to fit the wall.

The CRM can be applied to only one side, allowing *residents to remain largely undisturbed* in the building and *businesses to continue operating* during construction works. If the financial impact of temporarily relocating residents and interrupting business is considered, the *CRM is financially very competitive* (see §2.6).

CONS:

The method requires applying a *new layer over the entire wall surface*, which is not possible when extensive decorations are present or when the masonry is intended to remain visible.

The *direct costs (material and labour) of the CRM are not smaller* than for other strengthening technologies.

It can be *difficult to provide continuity of the reinforcement* in certain cases, such as changes to in cross-section or in presence of various obstacles.

Rough masonry surfaces (e.g., stone masonry) should first be levelled with a base layer of mortar to create a flat surface for the system application.

If the system is used with cement-based mortar, capillary suction can occur.

2.5. Dealing with structures under cultural heritage protection

Considering that cultural heritage (CH) historical buildings (such as palaces, residential buildings, churches, etc., which are mostly built of stone or brick masonry) are of special importance and significance for the human community, every intervention on such structures must be carried out with full respect for their material and non-material essence. Government and non-government agencies concerned with the protection of CH buildings have a duty to propose measures and supervise the execution of works to ensure that CH structures preserve their substance for future generations.

The Heritage Conservation Service promotes the integrity of protected buildings, considering three main elements:

- *Authenticity*. Refers to using genuine building materials consistent with the origin and dating of historic buildings. Checks are required to verify the source of materials and ensure they come from similar deposits, usually located near the construction sites. Laboratory tests determine the properties of materials and place them in specific historical contexts, which dictate their use in building renovation processes.
- *Reversibility*. It is important that renovation procedures are conducted in a way that enables the building to be restored to its original state without permanent damage. Reversible processes also promote more sustainable use of resources, as they do not cause irreparable harm and allow for the recovery or recycling of materials. Reversibility is therefore a key factor in ensuring that certain processes can be undertaken without lasting consequences.
- *Conservation*. This refers to the procedures, strategies, and approaches to conservation aimed at preserving original building elements with historical, cultural, aesthetic, or technical value, while ensuring that the building's authenticity is not compromised by construction interventions. It is important to preserve the features and details that give the building its historical significance, whether these include architectural elements, design features, or historic layers of construction. Conservation ensures that such buildings will survive for future generations.

One of the major challenges of interventions on a CH building is finding a balance between preserving its original historic character and adapting it for modern use and needs. In this sense, *structural interventions* must ensure the safety of CH structures for occupants even in the event of major natural threats (earthquakes, floods, etc.) by increasing their resilience to these hazards. In addition, actions aimed at improving *energy efficiency* (such as thermal insulation, energy retrofits, and upgrades to heating and electrical systems) are also important tasks to address in order to reduce the environmental impact of CH buildings.

As all these actions may affect the original structure or appearance, laws and regulations restrict the use of certain modern building materials and techniques, such as UNESCO standards or national cultural heritage legislation. Restoration should use materials and techniques consistent with those used when the building was constructed and should allow the

original materials to be restored as authentically as possible. However, despite the basic cultural and conservation principle of integrity, some compromises are necessary.

When applying the CONSTRAIN strengthening system to CH buildings, it is essential to consider that valuable decorative elements on interior or facade wall plasters may prevent intervention in those areas. In all cases, application procedures must be carried out with particular care for the original material. The removal of old plasters should be performed as gently as possible to minimise additional damage to the original wall construction. Special attention and care are required when drilling holes in historic brick or stone walls for CRM application. When drilling holes for transversal anchors, the drilling should be confined to the joints. Drilling directly into bricks or stones should be avoided whenever possible. The use of cement-based mortars must be excluded; instead, natural lime-based mortars should be used.

In Fig. 2.7-Fig. 2.9 some examples where the CONSTRAIN seismic strengthening method can or cannot be applied on CH building are presented.

Fig. 2.7 An example of a structure with interior historic wall paintings (a), and a facade (b) where CONSTRAIN strengthening can be applied only on the outer side of the wall.

Fig. 2.8 Building with extensive historic paintings on the facade (a) in no protected elements on the inside (b). CONSTRAIN strengthening can be applied on the inner side of the wall.

Fig. 2.9 Localized decorations, such as original historic paintings or stucco, must be preserved: the CONSTRAN strengthening can be applied excluding the decorated area or, if not consistent with reinforcement needs, the decoration and stucco or sculptures must be temporarily removed and placed back after strengthening is finished.

2.6. Is CRM financially competitive with other systems?

To assess the financial competitiveness of Composite Reinforced Mortar (CRM) compared to other systems, both direct and indirect costs, as well as social implications, need to be considered.

Among conventional solutions, the “steel mesh reinforced cement coating” [1], also known as “rete-betoncino” in Italy, remains one of the most widely used benchmarks. It consists of welded steel mesh-reinforced cement-based coatings on both sides of the wall. The coatings are connected through the wall by transverse steel anchors.

Reinforced-cement coatings must be applied to both sides of the walls; otherwise, they are not effective. This was clearly demonstrated in recent post-earthquake surveys, which showed asymmetric structural responses and detachment of the reinforced coating in such cases. In contrast, the CONSTRAIN project experimentally proved that CRM systems applied to only one side of the wall are, when properly designed, effective [2].

- ***Direct costs and durability***

Direct costs between two systems are compared in sample sheets, which show an analytical price breakdown. The sheets - provided in Annex A for illustrative purposes only - highlight the principal cost items and quantities that should be considered.

It should be noted that the calculations use galvanised steel components in the cement-based coating to ensure comparable system durability (45–50 years). Uncoated steel, which was widely used in the past, would modestly reduce material costs but drastically decrease durability due to corrosion (approximately 20–25 years), resulting in almost double the annual amortisation costs.

From the comparison of the direct costs for the basic techniques, it emerges that one-side CRM strengthening is approximately 30% cheaper than two-sides reinforced-cement coating. The higher cost of the fibre-based composite mesh is offset by lower material consumption and reduced labour time.

Additional costs arise for construction details dealing with structural discontinuity, such as anchoring into the foundation, across floors, and at wall corners and intersections. These costs are typically higher for the CRM technique, because of the use of fibre-based composite materials and stainless- steel threaded bars. The impact of these details on the total cost of the strengthening intervention varies from case to case, but does not significantly affect the price difference.

On the other hand, it is also evident that the two-sides reinforced-cement coating entails higher (pratically doubled) costs associated with the removal of existing plaster, masonry surface preparation, and application of finishes.

When CRM is applied to multi-leaf masonry walls, additional devices (such as artificial diatones) are required to connect the masonry leaves, ensuring masonry confinement. In these cases,

the direct costs of CRM become about 7% higher than those of two-sided reinforced cement coating.

The calculations show that the direct costs of CRM on both sides are almost 37% higher than those of reinforced-cement coating. Nevertheless, other factors and requirements, such as the mechanical and chemical compatibility with the masonry, should also be considered.

- ***Economic and social implications***

In addition to direct costs, other significant economic implications need to be considered when choosing strengthening interventions.

For example, reinforced-cement coating applied on both sides typically requires access to interior spaces and significant disruption to building occupants. This necessitates their temporary relocation, either partially or entirely, depending on building use, and incurs costs for alternative accommodation, lost productivity in commercial spaces, and management and coordination overheads.

The one-side CRM application significantly alleviates these issues. In many cases, the intervention can be performed externally with only minimal intervention from inside, resulting in lower non-construction expenses and indirect costs. In terms of inconvenience, it is comparable to any façade intervention. Indeed, it can be combined with a thermal insulation intervention, which occupants appreciate as they perceive direct and more noticeable savings.

Furthermore, when temporary relocation of occupants is required, various social costs and consequences arise. Relocation can significantly disrupt daily life, particularly for families with children, elderly residents, or individuals with limited mobility, and can lead to various forms of conflict. The loss of routine, proximity to services, and established social networks can cause stress and reduce overall well-being. International studies highlight an increase in depressive states and other health conditions. Temporary housing solutions may also result in lower living standards or overcrowding, further increasing discomfort and social vulnerability. In some cases, relocation may affect employment and education due to increased travel distances. The temporary relocation of residents can also weaken neighbourhood cohesion and create a perception of instability in the area. For public housing tenants, these effects may be even more pronounced due to pre-existing socio-economic vulnerabilities.

A more detailed and analytical assessment of the economic and social convenience of the one-side CRM application is presented in PRO-SIS Report 3.5 [3]).

In conclusion, when all cost categories are considered – direct installation costs, indirect social and operational costs, and amortisation – CRM can be a financially competitive solution. Its targeted application reduces total cost and minimises disruption to occupants.

3. INFORMATION FOR DESIGNERS

3.1. Inspection of the existing structure

Before any strengthening is planned, a structural engineer must inspect the building. The inspector should be provided with all existing documentation and given access to all areas relevant to the structural inspection. Information about past modifications to the structure should be obtained, possibly by interviewing residents or the owner. Generic data sources such as contemporary codes, standards, and documented practice can also be used. The inspector may propose to the owner that destructive or non-destructive tests be carried out to obtain the material parameters required for the structural assessment.

The engineer should write a report on the field investigations and measurements. The report should include the following information:

- Date of construction and any potential past renovations;
- Description of the building and its structural system;
- Description of the materials used;
- Description of the condition of the structure and a report on any observed damage;
- Data on the foundations and soil conditions at the site.

Potential damage, such as cracks, should be measured and documented. Most importantly, the cause of the cracks should be identified and a solution for repair should be proposed. Finally, any differences from the original plans should also be reported.

Based on the latest draft version of new generation of Eurocode 8-3 (Design of structures for earthquake resistance - Part 3: Assessment and retrofitting of buildings and bridges) the knowledge level (KL) about the structure is determined separately for:

- geometry (KLG);
- materials (KLM);
- structural details (KLD).

The knowledge level depends on the availability of documentation and the amount and quality of field surveys. There are three levels of knowledge (KL1, KL2, KL3), with KL1 being the lowest and KL3 the highest. To reach a certain KL, a specific number of surveys must be conducted. Further information about this is provided in the code. The purpose of the KL is to determine the values of safety factors and criteria for the inspecting engineer. For example, the lowest KL (KL1) is required for the assessment of a single-family house, whereas for a hospital, the highest KL (KL3) should be achieved.

In practical terms, the *geometry* can be checked by simple measurements for regular masonry structures, while for monuments or structures with complex layout the geometry can be obtained by laser scanning (high-definition surveying – HDS).

Regarding *structural details* in masonry structures, it is crucial to determine whether the tying of the structure is present and sufficient. Inspectors should check:

- Connections between floors and walls (e.g., whether wooden joists are tied to the walls or not);
- The presence of ties in the walls (such as steel bars at floor levels in walls or floors);
- The strength and rigidity of the floors (floors should be rigid in their plane to ensure seismic load distribution between all walls; old wooden floors are not sufficient).

To determine material parameters, the inspector should examine the typology of the masonry, the type of bricks or stones, the quality of mortar, and the quality of construction. Preferably, samples can be tested in the laboratory or in situ by destructive or non-destructive tests. The design values for strength verification should be obtained by reducing the characteristic or mean strength with a material safety factor. The procedure for obtaining material parameters is further explained in the next section.

The visual inspection of the structure is a crucial step of the field survey. The inspector should inspect the following properties of masonry:

- Type and texture of masonry (stone, brick, regular, irregular, etc.).
- The general state of masonry (physical/chemical degradation of bricks, material defects, alteration).
- Problems with localized degradation (molds, efflorescence, presence of climbing plant etc).
- Presence of irregularities in the masonry (flue tiles, tracks, etc.).
- Different material or different construction techniques.
- Change of original structure (opening/closing windows/doors, reduction of wall thickness and presence of concrete beams inside a wall etc.).
- Wrong or obsolete reinforcement.

3.2. Obtaining required material parameters

For historic masonry structures, there is usually very little original documentation and no information about material quality. The preferred and most reliable method for obtaining material parameters is always testing, either in situ or on samples extracted for laboratory analysis. For important structures that require a high KL, such as hospitals or schools, this approach is mandatory. Various tests are available. It is common to take brick samples, either whole or cores, and mortar samples for laboratory testing. More advanced, but less frequently used, methods include single or double flat jack tests to measure the stress, strength, and elastic modulus of masonry, as well as shove tests or diagonal compression tests to measure the shear strength of masonry.

For less important structures, testing may be prohibitively expensive or complicated, and in such cases, alternative approaches can be used. One method is to obtain this information from nearby structures built in the same period and had material properties.

A popular and convenient method is to find the information in a database. In Slovenia, the most popular source is the book by Prof. Tomaževič (*Potresno odporne Zidane stavbe*, Tehnis 2009). In Italy, a good source is the masonry database (<https://www.abacomurature.it/>). If none of the above sources is available, some values can usually be found in the codes (e.g., Eurocode, the Ministerial Circular correlated to the Italian National Building Code [4]-[5]).

The data required for seismic verification of existing buildings are:

- Elastic modulus.
- Shear modulus.
- Compressive strength.
- Shear strength (or tensile strength in diagonal compression).

3.3. Modelling of structures

When modelling masonry structures, it is necessary to create models to estimate the seismic resistance of the structure to in-plane loads, typically by constructing a global model of the structure, and to estimate the resistance of individual walls or parts of the structure to out-of-plane loads. In this section, the modelling of the entire structure to estimate the global response is presented. The modelling to estimate the out-of-plane response is presented in section 3.4.

The most common approach to modelling masonry structures for design and verification is the "Equivalent Frame Method" (EFM). This method is available in most commercial software for masonry structures, such as 3Muri, Midas Gen, PRO-SAP, and AMQUAKE.

The EFM assumes that walls are idealised by beam elements, as shown in Fig. 3.1a. Each beam represents the response of a wall segment, which is either pier, spandrel, or a rigid part of the wall. The segments are indicated by coloured areas in Fig. 3.1b: red areas represent rigid segments, grey areas are piers, and the dark yellow areas are spandrels. The pier height increases with the distance from the opening, at an angle of 30° (see Fig. 3.1a); this rule does not apply to spandrels. Further adjustments may be made to evaluate the effective pier height (i.e., the Dolce rule).

Fig. 3.1 Idealization of a wall according to Equivalent Frame Method.

The piers and spandrels exhibit a nonlinear response, which can represent different failure mechanisms, as explained in detail in section 0. The axes of the piers and spandrels are assumed to pass through the centre of gravity of the cross-section. The rigid segments are located at the massive joints between the piers and spandrels. These joints are typically so strong that damage is unlikely to occur there.

The structural model is typically three-dimensional, with floor structures modelled as either rigid or flexible diaphragms. Depending on the commercial software used for structural analysis, EFM models must be constructed manually by the user or are generated automatically from the structure's geometry. An example of the geometry of a 3D structural model and the corresponding generated EFM model is shown in Fig. 3.2.

Fig. 3.2 A 3D view of a masonry structure (a) and an EFM model (b) created in commercial software.

The EFM models are used to perform pushover analysis. In this analysis, the gravity loads are applied and kept constant, after which the lateral load is applied in a specific pattern (e.g., inverted triangle, according to the first vibration mode, constant, depending on the choice or software) and gradually increased until the structure collapses. The base shear as a function of the displacement at the control point (typically at the top of the structure) forms the pushover capacity curve, which can be compared to the demand on the structure to evaluate its response. To present the seismic load on the same graph, the design spectrum is plotted in acceleration-displacement format. Two approaches are commonly used: the N2 method or the Capacity Spectrum Method. This is further discussed in Section 0.

It should be noted that the EFM is suitable only for walls with a relatively uniform layout of openings. For structures with irregular patterns of openings, the method becomes less suitable and reliable. Thorough knowledge of the software, along with carefully considered and deliberate choices in model construction, is essential for obtaining reliable results.

3.4. Modelling of structural components for in-plane loads

List of symbols

Upper case letters:

A_{Fib}	Net area of fibres in a strand of FRP material
E	Equivalent elastic modulus of strengthened masonry
E_c	Elastic modulus of the mortar coating
E_{Fib}	Elastic modulus of fibres
E_m	Elastic modulus of masonry
G	Equivalent shear modulus of strengthened masonry
G_c	Shear modulus of mortar coating
G_m	Shear modulus of masonry
J	Second moment of area of the masonry cross-section
$K_{P,e}$	Initial (elastic) stiffness of pier
$K_{S,e}$	Initial (elastic) stiffness of spandrel
$M_{P,Rd(CRM)}$	Maximum resistance of pier to bending moment
$M_{P,Rd}^I$	Moment resistance of pier (type 1 failure)
$M_{P,Rd}^{II}$	Moment resistance of pier (type 2 failure)
$M_{P,Rd}^{III}$	Moment resistance of pier (type 3 failure)
$M_{S,Rd(CRM)}$	Maximum resistance of spandrel to bending moment
$M_{S,Rd}^I$	Moment resistance of spandrel (type 1 failure)
$M_{S,Rd}^{II}$	Moment resistance of spandrel (type 2 failure)
$M_{S,Rd}^{III}$	Moment resistance of spandrel (type 3 failure)
$M_{S,Rd(URM)}$	Resistance of URM spandrel to bending moment
$M_{S(URM+tie)}$	Resistance of semi-coupled strengthened spandrel to bending moment
$N_{P,d}$	Design axial (compressive) force in pier
$N_{S,d}$	Design axial (compressive) force in spandrel
V_P	Maximum in-plane resistance of pier to lateral force
$V_{P,d(CRM)}$	Resistance of strengthened pier to lateral force at diagonal shear failure
$V_{P,d(Fib)}$	Resistance provided by CRM coating to lateral force at diagonal shear failure
$V_{P,f(CRM)}$	Resistance of strengthened pier to lateral force at flexural failure
$V_{P(CRM)}$	Resistance of strengthened pier to in-plane lateral load
$V_{P(URM)}$	Resistance of URM pier to in-plane lateral load
$V_{P,d(URM)}$	Resistance of URM pier to lateral force at diagonal shear failure
V_S	Maximum in-plane resistance of spandrel to lateral force
$V_{S,d(CRM)}$	Resistance of spandrel to lateral force at diagonal shear failure
$V_{S,d(Fib)}$	Resistance provided by CRM coating to lateral force at diagonal shear failure
$V_{S,f(CRM)}$	Resistance of spandrel to lateral force at flexural failure
$V_{S(CRM)}$	Resistance of strengthened spandrel to in-plane lateral force
$V_{S(URM)}$	Resistance of URM spandrel to in-plane lateral load

Lower case letters:

d_{Fib}	Distance between extreme tension in strands and extreme compression in masonry
$d_{P,y}$	Maximum elastic displacement of pier

$d_{p,u}$	Ultimate displacement (i.e., displacement at near collapse) of pier
$d_{s,y}$	Maximum elastic displacement of spandrel
$d_{s,u}$	Ultimate displacement (i.e., displacement at near collapse) of spandrel
$f_{hm,cd}$	Design compressive strength of masonry in horizontal direction
$f_{m,cd}$	Design compressive strength of masonry
$f_{m,t}$	Tensile strength of masonry (obtained by diagonal compression test)
$f_{m,td}$	Design tensile strength of masonry (obtained by diagonal compression test)
$f_{t,eq}$	Equivalent masonry tensile strength
f_{v0}	Shear strength at zero compression (sliding shear along bed joints)
h_b	Brick or block height
h_p	Pier height
h_s	Height of the masonry part of the spandrel
i	Number of strengthened sides
l_{eff}	Effective length of interlocking at the spandrel extremities
l_{Fib}	Reference dimension of the pier/spandrel measured orthogonally to the shear force
l_p	Pier length (width)
l_s	Spandrel length
n_{Fib}	Number of horizontal strands of fibers crossing the diagonal crack
s	Strand spacing
t_c	Thickness of mortar coating
t	Thickness of masonry
t_{Fib}	Equivalent thickness of the tensile layer
y_n	Depth of neutral axis

Greek symbols:

α	Coefficient for boundary conditions
α_t	Reduction factor for fibres when stressed in shear
β	Slenderness ratio
$\varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$	Effective design tensile strain of fibres at failure
$\varepsilon_{m,y}$	Yield strain of masonry in compression
$\varepsilon_{m,u}$	Ultimate strain of masonry in compression
η	Coefficient for boundary conditions
λ	Reduction coefficient for the URM spandrel resistance after diagonal cracking
γ	Partial factor for the resistance model
χ	Reduction coefficient for unsymmetric reinforcement application
σ_0	Compressive stress in pier
σ_{p0}	Average compressive stress in the piers adjacent to the spandrel
τ_0	Shear strength at zero precompression
$\tau_{0,d}$	Design shear strength at zero precompression

3.4.1. Piers

The pier is usually between two openings on one floor as shown in Fig. 3.1. The dimensions of the pier (Fig. 3.3a) are length (l_p), masonry thickness (t), mortar coating thickness (t_c) and pier height (h_p). The CRM coating covers the entire surface and extends vertically beyond the pier.

The piers are loaded by vertical compressive force N , and exhibit a nonlinear response to the horizontal load V_p , as indicated by the black line in Fig. 3.3b. In the design process the nonlinear response is idealised by several linear segments, represented by the red line in Fig. 3.3b. The idealised response is defined by four values, each presented in a separate subsection:

- The elastic stiffness, $K_{p,e}$.
- The maximum resistance of pier to lateral force, V_p .
- The maximum elastic displacement, $d_{p,y}$.
- The ultimate displacement, $d_{p,u}$.

Fig. 3.3 The geometry of the pier (a), and the response of the pier to in-plane lateral load at the top of the pier (b)

The model of the pier in the EFM structure is schematically shown in Fig. 3.4. It consists of a vertical elastic beam element and nonlinear hinges. The rotational hinges at the bottom and top of the element reproduce flexural failure, while the hinge at mid-height reproduces shear failure. The response of both types of hinges is assumed to be bilinear.

The numerical model is the same for unstrengthened piers (i.e., piers without coating). However, the properties of such piers are much lower.

Fig. 3.4 The numerical model of a pier in equivalent frame method

- **Elastic stiffness $K_{p,e}$**

The computer programs based on the EFM capture the stiffness of the element by taking into account deformability of the elastic beam elements (see Fig. 3.4). To get realistic deflections, the elastic and shear modulus of masonry must correspond to the actual properties of the materials. The relation between the stiffness and the material and geometric properties of the pier are shown in Eq. 3.1.

$$\frac{1}{K_{p,e}} = \frac{h_p^3}{\eta \cdot J \cdot E} + \frac{1.2h_p}{G \cdot l_p \cdot t} \quad (3.1)$$

with η coefficient for boundary conditions (e.g. $\eta = 12$ for fixed-fixed type boundary conditions and $\eta = 3$ for cantilever) and J second moment of area of the masonry cross-section.

For unstrengthened (URM) piers, the elastic and shear moduli correspond to the masonry material. In the case of coating, the values must be adjusted:

$$E = \frac{t E_m + t_c E_c}{t} \quad (3.2)$$

$$G = \frac{t G_m + t_c G_c}{t} \quad (3.3)$$

where E and G are the effective moduli of the pier (with coating), normalised to the original thickness of the masonry, t . E_m and G_m are the elastic and shear moduli of masonry, while E_c and G_c are the elastic and shear moduli of the mortar of the coating; t_c is the thickness of the coating.

All properties are evaluated with respect to the original thickness of the masonry (t), and it is not necessary to modify the geometry of the structure when moving from the unstrengthened to the CRM-strengthened configuration. The moment of inertia of the cross section remains the same, but the bending stiffness of the cross-section increases because E is higher than E_m .

In structural analysis, whether response spectrum analysis or pushover, the stiffness of the structure is reduced to account for cracked cross-sections. This reduction is typically achieved by reducing the elastic and shear moduli by a factor of 0.5.

- **Resistance to lateral force V_p**

The CRM-strengthened masonry pier, loaded by vertical force N and subjected to an in-plane lateral load can fail either in diagonal shear (at a force $V_{p,d(CRM)}$) or in flexure (at a force $V_{p,f(CRM)}$). The lower of the two resistances should be considered in design:

$$V_{p(CRM)} = \min(V_{p,d(CRM)}; V_{p,f(CRM)}) \quad (3.4)$$

The lateral resistance should also not exceed the strength of the compressed strut:

$$V_{p(CRM)} \leq 0.25 \cdot l_p \cdot t \cdot f_{m,cd} \quad (3.5)$$

In the case of diagonal shear failure, the lateral resistance $V_{p,d(CRM)}$ is the sum of the resistances of the unstrengthened masonry, $V_{p,d(URM)}$, and the fibre reinforcement, $V_{p,d(Fib)}$:

$$V_{p,d(CRM)} = V_{p,d(URM)} + V_{p,d(Fib)} \quad (3.6)$$

The Turnšek Čačovič model can be used to calculate the resistance of URM piers to diagonal shear:

$$V_{P,d(URM)} = \frac{f_{m,td}}{\beta} \cdot l_p \cdot t \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_o}{f_{m,td}}} = \frac{1.5\tau_{0,d}}{\beta} \cdot l_p \cdot t \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_o}{1.5\tau_{0,d}}} \quad (3.7)$$

where $f_{m,td}$ is the design tensile strength of masonry obtained by the diagonal compression test (or cyclic shear compression test). Italian guidelines [5] allow the use of $f_{m,t} = 1.5 \tau_0$, where τ_0 is the shear strength at zero precompression corresponding to diagonal cracking through irregular masonry. It should be noted that τ_0 differs from f_{v0} as defined in Eurocode 6, which corresponds to sliding shear along bed joints. $f_{m,t}$ and f_{v0} are therefore not directly related, as they describe physically different material models. β in equation (3.7) is the ratio between the peak and average shear stress in the cross-section, which is normally evaluated from the slenderness ratio $1 \leq h_p/l_p \leq 1.5$. The compressive stress in the cross-section, σ_o , is calculated as $N_{P,d} / (t \cdot l_p)$, where the design compressive force $N_{P,d}$ is calculated using the seismic load combinations.

The shear resistance provided by CRM coating is calculated on the assumption that only fibres contribute to the strength at the maximum resistance limit state. This is based on the observation that the mortar cracks well before the maximum resistance is reached, and its contribution to resistance at this stage is negligible.

The horizontal fibres (strands of fibres) that run across the assumed diagonal crack contribute to the resistance. The strength provided by the horizontal strands of fibres is ideally the fracture strength of the fibres. In the case of CONSTRAIN strengthening, fibre fracture is likely to occur. However, if different types of failure are expected (such as fibre pull-out or delamination of the coating from the wall), the strength of the fibres is reduced in the calculation by reducing the ultimate strain.

The formula for calculation of strength of the CRM coating:

$$V_{P,d(Fib)} = \chi \cdot \frac{1}{\gamma} \cdot i \cdot A_{Fib} \cdot n_{Fib} \cdot \alpha_T \cdot \epsilon_{lim,Fib,d} \cdot E_{Fib} \quad (3.8)$$

Where:

- χ is the reduction coefficient that considers if the coating is applied unsymmetrically: $\chi = 1$ if the coating is on both sides and $\chi = 0.7$ if coating is only on one side. *CONSTRAIN tests indicate χ could be equal to 1 also for one sided application*; however, the number of tests was limited.
- γ is the partial factor for the resistance model (normally =2).
- i is the number of strengthened sides (1 or 2).
- A_{Fib} is the net cross section of a strand of FRP material.
- n_{Fib} is the number of horizontal strands crossing the diagonal crack. It can be calculated as l_{Fib}/s , where s is the strand spacing and l_{Fib} is the reference dimension of the pier measured orthogonally to the shear force (the pier height, h_p). The CNR-DT 215/2018 guidelines for FRCM systems [6] specify a limit for l_{Fib} , assuming that cracks cannot be at a steeper incline than 45° (max l_{Fib} is not greater than the pier's length, l_p). *The CONSTRAIN tests showed that cracks can develop at a steeper angle*; however, the number of tests was limited.

- α_T is a reduction factor that accounts for the reduced tensile strength of the fibres when stressed in shear. The reduction factor is assumed to be $\alpha_T = 0.8$; *CONSTRAIN tests indicate that this reduction is not necessary*; however, the number of tests was limited;
- $\varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$ is the design effective strain of the strands at failure. This value is obtained from lap shear tests and should be provided by the producer. *In the case of CONSTRAIN strengthening, this strain can be assumed equal to the ultimate strain at fracture*. The ultimate design strain can include reductions for exposure to aggressive environments (see [6] for details).
- E_{Fib} is the elastic modulus of the strands.

When checking the capacity of the pier in flexural failure, the resistance of a CRM strengthened masonry pier is calculated based on the following assumptions:

- composite action of CRM coating and masonry (monolithic cross-section);
- planar sections remain planar (Bernoulli hypothesis);
- zero tensile strength of masonry;
- bilinear response of masonry in compression (Fig. 3.5a);
- zero compressive strength of fibres;
- linear response of fibres in tension, up to fracture (Fig. 3.5b);
- the contribution of the mortar, in both tension and compression, is neglected;
- the effect of the asymmetry of the CRM coating is neglected (it can be implicitly taken into account by reduction coefficient χ applied to $\varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$).

In the plots of constitutive laws in Fig. 3.5, the following notation is introduced: $\varepsilon_{m,y}$ is the strain of masonry at the elastic limit (i.e. conventional yielding), $\varepsilon_{m,u}$ is the ultimate strain of masonry, and $\varepsilon_{lim,Fib}$ is the effective tensile strain of fibres at failure.

Fig. 3.5 The constitutive law of masonry (a) and of fibers (b).

The problem of calculating the bending resistance at a given axial load is therefore very similar to designing a reinforced concrete section. Any software for cross-section design can be used if it supports the constitutive models shown in Fig. 3.5.

If software is not available, analytical expressions may be used. The three cases are distinguished (Fig. 3.6), and the solution is the lowest of the three.

- *Type I*: masonry crushing at the compressive edge ($\varepsilon_m = \varepsilon_{m,u}$) and fibres in the elastic range ($\varepsilon_{Fib} < \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$):

$$M_{P,Rd}^I = f_{m,cd} \frac{t y_n}{2} \left[l_p (1 - k) - y_n (1 - k)^2 + k \left(\frac{l_p}{2} - y_n + \frac{2}{3} k y_n \right) \right] + \frac{\varepsilon_{m,u}}{y_n} E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \frac{(d_{Fib} - y_n)^2}{12} (2y_n + 4d_{Fib} - 3l_p) \quad (3.9)$$

$$k = \frac{\varepsilon_{m,y}}{\varepsilon_{m,u}} \quad (3.10)$$

$$y_n = \frac{N_{P,d} - E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{m,u} + \sqrt{N_{P,d}^2 + E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{m,u} [(2 - k)t \cdot d_{Fib} f_{m,cd} - 2N_{P,d}]}}{t f_{m,cd} (2 - k) - E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \varepsilon_{m,u}} \quad (3.11)$$

- *Type II*: tensile fracture of fibres ($\varepsilon_{Fib} = \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$) and masonry compressive strain in the plateau ($\varepsilon_{m,y} \leq \varepsilon_m \leq \varepsilon_{m,u}$):

$$M_{P,Rd}^{II} = f_{m,cd} \frac{t}{12} \left[2d_{Fib} y_n \xi (2\xi + 3) + 3l_p [y_n (2 + \xi) - \xi d_{Fib}] - 2y_n^2 (\xi^2 + 3 + 3\xi) - 2\xi^2 d_{Fib}^2 \right] + \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \frac{d_{Fib} - y_n}{12} (2y_n + 4d_{Fib} - 3l_p) \quad (3.12)$$

$$\xi = \frac{\varepsilon_{m,y}}{\varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}} \quad (3.13)$$

$$y_n = \frac{2 \cdot N_{P,d} + t \xi f_{m,cd} \cdot d_{Fib} + E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}}{t f_{m,cd} (2 + \xi) + E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}} \quad (3.14)$$

- *Type III*: tensile fracture of fibres ($\varepsilon_{Fib} = \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$) and linear stress distribution of masonry in compression ($\varepsilon_m < \varepsilon_{m,y}$):

$$M_{P,Rd}^{III} = \frac{t E_m \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}}{12} \frac{y_n^2}{d_{Fib} - y_n} (3l_p - 2y_n) + \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \frac{d_{Fib} - y_n}{12} (2y_n + 4d_{Fib} - 3l_p) \quad (3.15)$$

$$y_n = \frac{N_{P,d} + E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} - \sqrt{N_{P,d}^2 + E_m \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} d_{Fib} t (E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} + 2N_{P,d})}}{\varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} (E_{Fib} t_{Fib} - t E_m)} \quad (3.16)$$

- $M_{P,Rd}$ is the design bending moment resistance of the pier;
- $N_{P,d}$ is the design axial (compressive) force of the pier;
- y_n is the depth of neutral axis;
- t is thickness of masonry;
- d_{Fib} is distance between extreme tension in strands and extreme compression in masonry;
- t_{Fib} is the equivalent thickness of the tensile layer = $i A_{Fib} / s$;
- i is the number of strengthened sides (1 or 2);
- A_{Fib} is the net cross section of a strand of FRP material;
- s is the strand spacing

The pier's lateral resistance associated to the in-plane bending failure is calculated as:

$$V_{p,f(CRM)} = \frac{\alpha M_{P,Rd(CRM)}}{h_p} \quad (3.17)$$

where α is the parameter for the boundary conditions (e.g. $\alpha=1$ for fixed-fixed boundary conditions and $\alpha=2$ for cantilever boundary conditions).

Fig. 3.6 Strain and stress distribution into the CRM strengthened masonry cross section, for the three different cases.

It is observed that CRM strengthening increases the flexural capacity of the pier only if it is properly anchored or extended at the ends. Otherwise, the reinforcement is ineffective, and the flexural resistance is evaluated as for the unstrengthened configuration.

The flexural resistance of URM pier can be calculated by the following formula:

$$M_{P,Rd(URM)} = \sigma_0 \frac{t \cdot l_p^2}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_0}{0.85 f_{m,cd}} \right), \quad (3.18)$$

where $f_{m,cd}$ is the design compressive strength of masonry.

- **Elastic displacement $d_{p,y}$**

The elastic displacement $d_{p,y}$ (also called the conventional yield displacement) is calculated from the shear force V_P and the elastic stiffness $K_{p,e}$:

$$d_{p,y} = \frac{V_P}{K_{p,e}}. \quad (3.19)$$

- **Ultimate displacement $d_{p,u}$**

The codes and guidelines do not provide a direct answer. For reinforced masonry, which differs from CRM-strengthened masonry, the limits specified in the Italian codes [4] are $0.008 \cdot h_p$ for walls failing in shear and $0.016 \cdot h_p$ for walls failing in bending.

Tests show that for CONSTRAIN strengthening, $d_{p,u} = 0.01 \cdot h_p$ can be used for piers failing in shear, and $d_{p,u} = 0.02 \cdot h_p$ can be used for piers failing in bending. This assumption is valid for walls strengthened on one or both sides. However, the number of tests was limited.

3.4.2. Spandrels

The spandrels are the horizontal elements between the piers, as shown in Fig. 3.1. Their primary function is to support the floor structures above windows and doors. Because masonry has almost no capacity for tensile loads, the spandrel is supported by a wooden lintel or a masonry arch. The spandrels can also provide a coupling effect to the piers.

The dimensions of the spandrel (Fig. 3.7a) are length (l_s), masonry thickness (t), mortar coating thickness (t_c), and height of the masonry part of the spandrel (h_s). The CRM coating covers the entire surface and extends beyond the spandrel.

The spandrels are not loaded axially and exhibit a nonlinear response to the lateral load V_s , as indicated by the black lines in Fig. 3.7c. During the design process, this nonlinear response is idealised by linear segments, shown by the red line in Fig. 3.7c. The idealised response is defined by four values, each presented in a separate subsection:

- The elastic stiffness, $K_{s,e}$;
- The maximum resistance of spandrel to lateral force, V_s .
- The maximum elastic displacement, $d_{s,y}$;
- The ultimate displacement, $d_{s,u}$.

Fig. 3.7: (a) The geometry of the spandrel, with (b) detail of forces acting on the spandrel and (c) the response of CONSTRAN strengthened the spandrel.

The model of the spandrel in the EFM structure is schematically shown in Fig. 3.8. It consists of a horizontal elastic beam element and nonlinear hinges. The rotational hinges at the lateral extremities of the element can reproduce flexural failure, while the hinge at the centre can reproduce shear failure.

Fig. 3.8 The numerical model of a spandrel in equivalent frame method.

- **Elastic stiffness $K_{S,e}$**

Computer programmes based on the EFM capture the stiffness of the element by considering the deformability of the elastic beam elements (see Fig. 3.9). To obtain realistic deflections, the elastic and shear moduli of masonry must correspond to the actual properties of the materials.

$$\frac{1}{K_{S,e}} = \frac{l_S^3}{\eta \cdot J \cdot E} + \frac{1.2 \cdot l_S}{G \cdot h_S \cdot t} \quad (3.20)$$

with η coefficient for boundary conditions (e.g., $\eta = 12$ for fixed-fixed boundary conditions and $\eta = 3$ for cantilever) and J , the second moment of area of the masonry cross-section.

For unstrengthened (URM) piers, the elastic and shear moduli correspond to the masonry material. In the case of coating, the values must be adjusted accordingly:

$$E = \frac{t \cdot E_m + t_c \cdot E_c}{t} \quad (3.21)$$

$$G = \frac{t \cdot G_m + t_c \cdot G_c}{t} \quad (3.22)$$

where E and G are the effective moduli of the spandrel (with coating), normalised to the original thickness of the masonry, t . E_m and G_m are the elastic and shear moduli of masonry, and E_c and G_c are the elastic and shear moduli of the mortar of the coating; t_c is the thickness of the coating.

All properties are evaluated with respect to the original thickness of the masonry (t), and it is not necessary to modify the geometry of the structure when moving from the unstrengthened to the CRM-strengthened configuration. The moment of inertia of the cross-section remains the same, but the bending stiffness increases because E is higher than E_m .

In structural analysis, whether response spectrum analysis or pushover, the stiffness of the structure is reduced to account for cracked cross-sections. This reduction is typically achieved by reducing the elastic and shear moduli by a factor of 0.5.

- **Resistance to lateral force V_S**

The CRM strengthened masonry spandrel subjected to in-plane load can fail either in diagonal shear (at a force $V_{S,d(CRM)}$) or in flexure (at a force $V_{S,f(CRM)}$). The lowest of the two resistances should be considered in design:

$$V_{S(CRM)} = \min(V_{S,d(CRM)}; V_{S,f(CRM)}) \quad (3.23)$$

The resistance should also not exceed the strength of the compressed strut:

$$V_{S(CRM)} \leq 0.25 \cdot h_s \cdot t \cdot f_{m,cd} \quad (3.24)$$

In the case of diagonal shear failure, the resistance $V_{S,d(CRM)}$ is the sum of the reduced resistance of unstrengthened masonry, $\lambda \cdot V_{S,d(URM)}$, and the resistance of fibre-based meshes, $V_{S,d(Fib)}$:

$$V_{S,d(CRM)} = \lambda \cdot V_{S,d(URM)} + V_{S,d(Fib)} \quad (3.25)$$

where $\lambda \leq 1$ is a coefficient accounting for the reduction of resistance after diagonal cracking in the masonry (= 0.6 for reinforced concrete or steel lintel, 0.4 for timber lintel, 0.1 for masonry arch).

The Turnšek Čačovič model can be used to calculate the resistance of URM spandrels to diagonal shear is:

$$V_{S,d(URM)} = \frac{f_{m,td}}{\beta} h_s \cdot t \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_o}{f_{m,td}}} = \frac{1.5\tau_{o,d}}{\beta} h_s \cdot t \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_o}{1.5\tau_{o,d}}}, \quad (3.26)$$

where $f_{m,td}$ is the design tensile strength of masonry obtained by the diagonal compression test (or cyclic shear compression test). Italian guidelines [5] allow the use $f_{m,t} = 1.5 \tau_o$, where τ_o is the shear strength at zero precompression corresponding to diagonal cracking through irregular masonry. It should be noted that τ_o differs from f_{v0} as defined in Eurocode 6, which corresponds to sliding shear along bed joints. $f_{m,t}$ and f_{v0} are therefore not directly related, as they describe physically different material models. β in equation (3.26) is the ratio between the peak and average shear stress in the cross section, which is normally evaluated from the slenderness ratio $1 \leq l_s/h_s \leq 1.5$. The compressive stress in the cross-section, σ_o , is calculated as $N_{s,d} / (t h_s)$, where the design compressive force $N_{s,d}$ is calculated using the seismic load combinations. However, it is usually assumed to be zero because of negligible axial force in the spandrel; in this case the square root term equals one.

The shear resistance provided by CRM coating is calculated on the assumption that only fibres contribute to the strength at the maximum resistance limit state. This is based on the observation that the mortar cracks well before the maximum resistance is reached, and its contribution to resistance at this stage is negligible.

The vertical fibres (strands of fibres) that run across the assumed diagonal crack contribute to the resistance. The strength provided by the vertical strands of fibres is ideally the fracture strength of the fibres. *In the case of CONSTRAIN strengthening, fibre fracture is likely to occur.* However, if different types of failure are expected (such as fibre pull-out or delamination of the coating from the wall), the strength of the fibres is reduced in the calculation by lowering the ultimate strain.

The formula for calculation of strength of the CRM coating:

$$V_{S,Fib} = \chi \frac{1}{\gamma} \cdot i \cdot A_{Fib} \cdot n_{Fib} \cdot \alpha_T \cdot \varepsilon_{lim, Fib,d} \cdot E_{Fib} \quad (3.27)$$

where:

- χ is the reduction coefficient that accounts for whether the coating is applied unsymmetrically: $\chi = 1$ if the coating is on both sides and $\chi = 0.7$ if the coating is only on one

side. *CONSTRAIN tests indicate that χ could be equal to 1 for one or two sided application; however, the number of tests was limited;*

- γ is the partial factor for the resistance model (normally =2);
- i is the number of strengthened sides (1 or 2);
- A_{Fib} is the net cross section of a strand of FRP material;
- n_{Fib} is the number of vertical strands crossing the diagonal crack. It can be calculated as I_{Fib}/s , where s is the strand spacing and I_{Fib} the reference dimension of the spandrel measured orthogonally to the shear force (the spandrel length, l_s). The CNR-DT 215/2018 guidelines for FRCM systems [6] provide a limit for I_{Fib} , which assumes that cracks cannot be at a steeper incline than 45° (max I_{Fib} is not greater than the spandrel's height, h_s). *The CONSTRAIN tests showed that cracks can develop at a steeper angle; however, the number of tests was limited;*
- α_T is a reduction factor that accounts for the reduced tensile strength of the fibres when stressed in shear. The reduction factor is assumed to be $\alpha_T = 0.8$; *CONSTRAIN tests indicate this reduction is not necessary; however, the number of tests was limited;*
- $\varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$ is the design effective strain of strands at failure. This value is obtained by lap shear tests and should be provided by the producer. *In the case of CONSTRAIN strengthening, this strain can be assumed equal to ultimate strain at fracture.* The the ultimate design strain can include reductions for exposure to aggressive environment (see [6] for details).
- E_{Fib} is the elastic modulus of the strands.

When calculating the capacity of spandrels in flexural failure, the resistance of CRM strengthened masonry spandrels is calculated based on the following assumptions:

- composite action of the CRM coating and the masonry (monolithic cross-section);
- planar sections remain planar (Bernoulli hypothesis);
- zero tensile strength of masonry;
- bilinear response of masonry in compression (Fig. 3.9a);
- zero compressive strength of fibres;
- linear response of fibres in tension, up to fracture (Fig. 3.9b);
- the contribution of the mortar, in both tension and compression, is neglected;
- the effect of the asymmetry of the CRM coating is neglected (it can be implicitly accounted for by a reduction coefficient χ applied to $\varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$).

In the plots of constitutive laws (Fig. 3.9), the following notation is introduced: $\varepsilon_{m,y}$ is the strain of masonry at the elastic limit (i.e. conventional yielding), $\varepsilon_{m,u}$ is the ultimate strain of masonry, and $\varepsilon_{lim,Fib}$ is the effective strain of fibres at failure.

Fig. 3.9 The constitutive law of masonry (a) and of fibers (b).

The problem of calculating the bending resistance in the absence of axial load is therefore very similar to designing a reinforced concrete section. Any software for cross-section design can be used if it supports the constitutive models shown in Fig. 3.9.

If software is not available, analytical expressions can be used. The three cases are distinguished (Fig. 3.10), and the solution is the lowest of the three.

- *Type I*: masonry crushing at the compressive edge ($\varepsilon_m = \varepsilon_{m,u}$) and fibres in the elastic range ($\varepsilon_{Fib} < \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$):

$$M_{S,Rd}^I = f_{m,cd} \frac{t y_n}{2} \left[h_s (1 - k) - y_n (1 - k)^2 + k \left(\frac{h_s}{2} - y_n + \frac{2}{3} k y_n \right) \right] + \frac{\varepsilon_{m,u}}{y_n} E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \frac{(d_{Fib} - y_n)^2}{12} (2y_n + 4d_{Fib} - 3h_s) \quad (3.28)$$

$$k = \frac{\varepsilon_{m,y}}{\varepsilon_{m,u}} \quad (3.29)$$

$$y_n = \frac{N_{S,d} - E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{m,u} + \sqrt{N_{S,d}^2 + E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{m,u} [(2 - k)t \cdot d_{Fib} f_{m,cd} - 2N_{S,d}]}}{t f_{m,cd} (2 - k) - E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \varepsilon_{m,u}} \quad (3.30)$$

- *Type II*: tensile fracture of fibres ($\varepsilon_{Fib} = \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$) and masonry compressive strain in the plateau ($\varepsilon_{m,y} \leq \varepsilon_m \leq \varepsilon_{m,u}$):

$$M_{S,Rd}^{II} = f_{m,cd} \frac{t}{12} \left[2d_{Fib} y_n \xi (2\xi + 3) + 3h_s [y_n (2 + \xi) - \xi d_{Fib}] - 2y_n^2 \cdot (\xi^2 + 3 + 3\xi) - 2\xi^2 d_{Fib}^2 \right] + \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \frac{d_{Fib} - y_n}{12} (2y_n + 4d_{Fib} - 3h_s) \quad (3.31)$$

$$\xi = \frac{\varepsilon_{m,y}}{\varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}} \quad (3.32)$$

$$y_n = \frac{2 \cdot N_{S,d} + t \xi f_{m,cd} \cdot d_{Fib,d} + E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}}{t f_{m,cd} (2 + \xi) + E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}} \quad (3.33)$$

- *Type III*: tensile fracture of fibers ($\varepsilon_{Fib} = \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$) and linear stress distribution of masonry in compression ($\varepsilon_m < \varepsilon_{m,y}$):

$$M_{S,Rd}^{III} = \frac{t E_m \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}}{12} \frac{y_n^2}{d_{Fib} - y_n} (3h_s - 2y_n) + \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \frac{d_{Fib} - y_n}{12} (2y_n + 4d_{Fib} - 3h_s) \quad (3.34)$$

$$y_n = \frac{N_{S,d} + E_f t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} - \sqrt{N_{S,d}^2 + E_m \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} d_{Fib} t_{Fib} (E_f t_{Fib} d_f \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} + 2N_{S,d})}}{\varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} (E_{Fib} t_{Fib} - t E_m)} \quad (3.35)$$

- $M_{S,Rd}$ is the design bending moment resistance of the spandrel;
- $N_{S,d}$ is the design axial (compressive) force of the spandrel (usually assumed 0);
- y_n is the depth of neutral axis;
- t is thickness of masonry;
- d_{Fib} is distance between extreme tension in strands and extreme compression in masonry;
- t_{Fib} is the equivalent thickness of the tensile layer = $i A_{Fib} / s$;
- i is the number of strengthened sides (1 or 2);

- A_{Fib} is the net cross section of a strand of FRP material;
- s is the strand spacing.

Fig. 3.10 Strain and stress distribution in CRM strengthened masonry cross section for the three different cases.

The spandrel's resistance to in-plane bending failure is calculated as:

$$V_{S,f(CRM)} = \frac{\alpha M_{S,Rd(CRM)}}{l_s}, \quad (3.36)$$

where α is the parameter for the boundary conditions (e.g. $\alpha = 1$ for fixed-fixed boundary conditions and $\alpha = 2$ for cantilever boundary conditions). It is observed that CRM strengthening increases the flexural capacity of the spandrel only if it is properly anchored or extended over the ends. Otherwise, the reinforcement is ineffective, and the flexural resistance is evaluated as for the unstrengthened configuration (shown below).

The flexural resistance of URM spandrel is low and can be calculated using the following formulas:

$$M_{S,Rd(URM)} = \frac{2}{3} f_{t,eq} \cdot t \cdot h_b \cdot h_s \cdot \rho, \quad \text{with } \rho = h_s / 4h_b \quad (3.37)$$

where $f_{t,eq}$ is the equivalent tensile strength (Fig. 3.11), calculated as:

$$f_{t,eq} = \frac{l_{eff}}{h_b} (f_{v0} + 0.65 \cdot \sigma_{0P}), \quad (3.38)$$

where l_{eff} is the effective interlocking length, h_b the height of the brick, f_{v0} the shear strength at zero pre-compression, and σ_{0P} the average compressive stress in the adjacent piers. In the case of stone masonry, the values of the effective interlocking length and stone height may be assumed as average values, based on visual inspection of the masonry. In the case of poor masonry, the bending strength of the spandrel can be neglected.

When the flexural resistance is reached at $d_{s,y}$, vertical cracks appear at the spandrel ends and a sudden drop in resistance occurs (Fig. 3.11b). The residual strength after cracking due to friction is obtained by assuming $f_{v0} = 0$ in Eq. (3.38).

Fig. 3.11 Bending resistance mechanism in of unreinforced spandrel (a) and typical response to lateral load (b).

A masonry spandrel can benefit from the coupling effect of a horizontal tie element (such as a steel bar or a reinforced concrete beam), which provides the spandrel with strength and ductility. In this case, the bending resistance can be calculated the following formula:

$$M_{S,Rd(URM+tie)} = H_P \frac{h_S}{2} \left(1 - \frac{H_P}{0.85 f_{hm,cd} h_S t} \right), \quad (3.39)$$

where H_P is the minimum between the tensile resistance of the tie element and $0.4 \cdot f_{hm,cd} \cdot h_S \cdot t$, where $f_{hm,cd}$ is the design compressive strength of masonry in the horizontal direction.

- **Elastic displacement $d_{s,y}$**

The elastic displacement $d_{s,y}$ (also called conventional yield displacement) is calculated from shear force V_S and elastic stiffness $K_{S,e}$:

$$d_{s,y} = \frac{V_S}{K_{S,e}} \quad (3.40)$$

- **Ultimate displacement $d_{s,u}$**

The codes and guidelines do not provide a direct answer. However, according to the Italian guidelines [5], for spandrels with tensile-resistant devices (such as ties or CRM coating), the limits are $0.015 \cdot l_s$ for shear failure and $0.020 \cdot l_s$ for bending failure.

Tests shows that for *CONSTRAIN* strengthening, $d_{s,u} = 0.030 \cdot l_s$ can be used for spandrels failing in either shear or bending. This assumption is valid for walls strengthened on one or both sides. However, the number of tests was limited.

3.5. Interpretation of results and presenting compliance criteria

As mentioned in Section 0, the usual procedure for assessing the seismic resistance of masonry buildings, whether existing or strengthened, is to perform nonlinear pushover analysis.

The result of the pushover analysis is the capacity curve, which shows base shear (or acceleration) as a function of the displacement at the top of the structure. Additionally, a detailed state of the structure is obtained for each point on the pushover curve, indicating which elements are damaged, the extent of the damage, and whether the damage is due to shear or bending. An example is shown in Fig. 3.12, which depicts a structure under a particular lateral load. Elements marked with dark blue circles are undamaged, light blue elements are lightly damaged, orange elements are heavily damaged, and red elements have failed. Different colours or markings may be used depending on the software. Such graphical illustrations are crucial for identifying and quantifying damage in the structure.

Fig. 3.12 State of the structure at a particular level of horizontal load: (a) shear damage and (b) bending damage.

To compare the capacity curve of the structure with the seismic demand (inelastic spectrum in acceleration-displacement format), it must be converted into the response of a single-degree-of-freedom (SDOF) model. The procedure for this transformation is described in building codes (e.g., Eurocode 8-1, Annex B). The performance point corresponding to the attainment of a given performance criterion (i.e., limit state) can be shown on the capacity curve or on the simplified, equivalent bilinear capacity curve.

Commercial software usually uses either the N2 method or the Capacity Spectrum method to compare seismic demand and capacity in an Acceleration–Displacement Response Spectrum (ADRS) graph (Fig. 3.13).

If the software is based on the N2 method (Fig. 3.13a), the original demand is defined by the elastic response spectrum for the site and the design earthquake for the considered limit state. The elastic spectrum is then converted into an inelastic spectrum, based on the period of vibration of the idealised SDOF system response (T^*) and the equal energy (if $T^* < T_C$) or equal displacement (if $T^* \geq T_C$) criteria. The intersection of the inelastic demand spectrum and the

idealised SDOF response curve gives the target point, which indicates the expected displacement and damage in the structure for the considered seismic load.

On the other hand, if the software uses the Capacity Spectrum Method (Fig. 3.13b), the demand spectrum is damped according to the equivalent viscous damping of the structure at the attainment of the specified target displacement. Analytical formulations are provided in codes and literature to calculate the damping of masonry structures, which usually increases asymptotically with the target displacement, within the range of 5% to 20%. The target point is defined by the intersection of the damped demand spectrum with the capacity curve.

In both approaches, the structure withstands the design earthquake if the target point, representing demand, is to the left of the performance point, representing capacity.

Fig. 3.13 Example of capacity curve by (a) the N2- method and (b) the Capacity spectrum method.

3.6. Local behaviour (out-of-plane)

Out-of-plane (OOP) bending action induced by seismic loads may trigger local damage or collapse. Such damage is very dangerous, as the resulting debris poses a threat to people and property. The risk of local collapse is highest for structures without ties, in cases of poorly laid masonry, which tends to disaggregate, and in multiple-leaf masonry with unconnected leaves. OOP failure is very difficult to predict, because OOP loads are highest at the top floors, but post-earthquake observations show that OOP failure often occurs only after walls have been damaged by in-plane loads.

The application of CONSTRAIN strengthening is an effective strategy to prevent out-of-plane collapse of masonry walls, as the FRP material on the tension side increases the bending strength of the masonry cross-section. Furthermore, CONSTRAIN strengthening inherently provides tying and improves the connection of the wall leaves. It is especially effective in the case of two-sided coating, which almost entirely prevents out-of-plane collapse.

The problem of calculating the OOP bending resistance of a CRM-strengthened masonry cross-section at a given axial load is very similar to designing a reinforced concrete section, and can be evaluated on the basis of the following assumptions:

- composite action of CRM coating and the masonry (monolithic cross-section);
- planar sections remain planar (Bernoulli hypothesis);
- zero tensile strength of masonry;
- bilinear response of masonry in compression (Fig. 3.16a);
- zero compressive strength of fibres;
- linear response of fibres in tension, up to fracture (Fig. 3.16b);
- the contribution of the mortar, in tension (and, to be on the safe side, also in compression), is neglected;

Fig. 3.14 The constitutive law of masonry (a) and of fibers (b).

Failure due to masonry crushing or reaching the limit tensile strain of the fibres (with masonry in either the elastic or plastic stage) can occur, depending on the mechanical characteristics of the masonry and CRM, the wall thickness, and the applied axial load. For the out-of-plane bending resistance mechanism to activate, the masonry should not fail prematurely in shear at the cracked sections.

Any software for cross-section design may be used if it supports the constitutive models shown in Fig. 3.14. If such software is unavailable, analytical expressions may be used. The three cases are distinguished (Fig. 3.15), and the solution is the lowest value among them.

- *Type I*: masonry crushing at the compressive edge and fibers in the elastic range;
- *Type II*: tensile fracture of fibers and masonry compressive strain in the plateau;
- *Type III*: tensile fracture of fibers and linear stress distribution of masonry in compression.

Fig. 3.15 Strain and stress distribution into the CRM strengthened masonry cross section, for the three different cases.

Once CONSTRAIN strengthening is applied, failure occurs over the height of a storey. One possible approach to estimate the OOP capacity of walls is to assume one of the mechanisms shown in Fig. 3.16. The beneficial effect of vertical stress can be taken into account.

The mechanisms in Fig. 3.16 show that, particularly for CRM one-sided applications, ensuring the continuity of the reinforcement is crucial, so that the CRM reinforcement remains effective even when deflection occurs towards the unstrengthened surface. Adequate transverse anchoring is also important to prevent wall disintegration.

Fig. 3.16 Possible mechanisms for estimating OOP capacity of walls (piers) between two stories. (a) and (b) are cases of floors that have strong connection at the base and bottom, (c) is the case of top floor with flexible connection at the top.

3.7. Structural details and design drawings with explanations

3.7.1. *Strengthening of single leaf walls*

The basic CONSTRAIN strengthening of single-leaf walls consists of a 3 cm thick mortar coating, reinforced with a GFRP mesh and anchored by L-shaped GFRP connectors. The areas around the connectors are further strengthened with additional 15 × 15 cm patches of GFRP mesh to improve stress distribution. To ensure continuity of reinforcement in stress transfer, the GFRP meshes must overlap by at least 20 cm and be anchored at wall intersections, into foundations, and across floors.

If strengthening is applied to both sides of the wall (Fig. 3.17), first, 24 mm diameter holes for the L connectors (6/m²) are drilled through the wall. If the anchor overlap is close to the wall surface, the remaining part of the hole may have a reduced diameter (about 16 mm). In all cases, the minimum splice overlap length between the two connectors must be ensured. It is advisable and good practice to drill into the mortar joints. Finally, the holes must be completely injected with resin to ensure the effectiveness of the transverse connection.

At wall intersections and corners, angular GFRP mesh elements shall be used to ensure reinforcement continuity. A minimum overlap between angular elements and regular meshes must be provided, and additional connectors must be placed in the overlap region.

When the CONSTRAIN strengthening is applied to only one side of the masonry (Fig. 3.18) of single-leaf walls, the anchors are installed only on the side with the mortar coating. The 16 mm diameter holes for the GFRP L connectors (6/m²) are drilled to a depth of at least two-thirds of the masonry thickness. The front view of the coating is shown in Fig. 3.19.

Fig. 3.17 Two-sided CONSTRAIN strengthening of a single leaf wall.

Fig. 3.18 One-sided CONSTRAN strengthening of a single leaf wall.

SEC. A-A for CRM reinforcement on both sides

SEC. A-A for CRM reinforcement on one side

- 1 - GFRP mesh
- 2 - GFRP mesh device
- 3 - GFRP L-shape connector
- 4 - Existing masonry
- 5 - Mortar coating
- 6 - Steel diatons

Fig. 3.19 Front view of the CONSTRAN strengthening on a single leaf wall.

3.7.2. Strengthening of double leaf walls

If the masonry has multiple leaves and the CONSTRAIN strengthening is applied to only one side, the leaves must be connected by artificial diatones in addition to L-shaped connectors. One-sided application of CONSTRAIN strengthening on double-leaf stone masonry is shown in Fig. 3.20. The sketch of the front view is shown in Fig. 3.21.

Artificial diatones are constructed by core drilling, usually with a diameter of 50 mm and a depth of at least two-thirds of the masonry thickness. The hole is filled with thixotropic mortar with high mechanical performance and a stainless-steel threaded bar. At the end of the bar, a thick stainless-steel washer of about 150 mm in diameter is installed, featuring several circular holes to improve adhesion with the mortar coating and to create an effective connection between the GFRP mesh and the coating.

Fig. 3.20 One-sided CONSTRAIN strengthening of a multiple leaves wall.

SEC. A-A

- 1 - GFRP mesh
- 2 - GFRP mesh device
- 3 - GFRP L-shape connector
- 4 - Existing masonry
- 5 - Mortar coating
- 6 - Artificial diaton

SEC. B-B

Fig. 3.21 Front view of the one-sided CONSTRAIN strengthening on a multiple leaves wall.

3.7.3. *Anchoring of coating*

For the CONSTRAIN strengthening to be effective, it must be anchored into the foundations and be continuous through floors and wall intersections. To provide anchorage into the foundations and through floors and walls, stainless steel bars are used. The bars are installed below the GFRP mesh to prevent splitting of the mortar. The GFRP connectors should be placed near the edge of the wall to effectively connect the mesh reinforcement with the stainless-steel anchors. The minimum bond length for the bars must be ensured.

- ***Anchoring into the foundation***

The stainless-steel anchors are embedded in the mortar coating at one end and anchored to the foundation by resin injection at the other, as shown in Fig. 3.22. The anchoring to the foundation is achieved by inclined holes in the foundations.

Anchoring the coating into the foundation is often complicated due to the absence or very poor quality of foundations. To achieve the required anchoring, the foundations may need to be upgraded with additional reinforced concrete beams. In this case, the stainless-steel bars are embedded in the reinforced concrete beam.

- ***Anchoring through floors***

For the coating to be effective, the continuity of the mesh must be maintained between floors. This is achieved by vertical stainless-steel bars embedded in the mortar coating and anchored to the floor slab by resin injection, as shown in Fig. 3.23.

- ***Anchoring across wall intersections***

For the two-sided CONSTRAIN reinforcement, the L-shaped GFRP anchors effectively tie the masonry at "T-shape" wall intersections, and generally no additional anchors are required.

Conversely, for the one-sided CONSTRAIN reinforcement, horizontal stainless steel bars must be installed along the full height of the wall. These anchors must be embedded in the mortar coating, and the holes drilled through the wall must be injected with resin, as shown in Fig. 3.24. For the unsymmetrical intersection (right side of the figure), a nut with washer and a GFRP mesh device must be added.

Legend:

- | | |
|----------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| 1 - GFRP mesh | 5 - Mortar coating |
| 2 - GFRP mesh device | 6 - Anchoring stainless steel bar |
| 3 - GFRP L-shape connector | 7 - Drilled hole injected with resin |
| 4 - Existing masonry | 8 - Artificial diaton |

Fig. 3.22 Anchoring CONSTRAN coating into foundation.

Legend:

- | | |
|----------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| 1 - GFRP mesh | 5 - Mortar coating |
| 2 - GFRP mesh device | 6 - Anchoring stainless steel bar |
| 3 - GFRP L-shape connector | 7 - Drilled hole injected with resin |
| 4 - Existing masonry | 8 - Existing floor |

Fig. 3.23 Anchoring CONSTRAIN coating across intermediate floors.

Symmetric "T-shape" intersection

Unsymmetric "T-shape" intersection

Legend:

- | | |
|----------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| 1 - GFRP mesh | 5 - Mortar coating |
| 2 - GFRP mesh device | 6 - Anchoring stainless steel bar |
| 3 - GFRP L-shape connector | 7 - Drilled hole injected with resin |
| 4 - Existing masonry | 8 - Nut with washer |

Fig. 3.24 Anchoring CONSTRAIN coating at wall intersections.

3.8. Maintenance plan of the interventions: contents and prescriptions

The maintenance plan is a complementary document to the design project that outlines and schedules maintenance activities to preserve functionality, quality characteristics, efficiency, and economic value over time.

The maintenance plan is composed by:

- *User manual.* The user manual provides correct usage information to prevent damage from improper use and to inform the user of the consequences of interventions on the structure, particularly on the CRM coating.

User manual

It is prescribed not to make changes to the structures without prior design by a qualified technician and not to exceed the maximum overloads envisaged both during the normal operation of the structure, events overtime and during any maintenance operations.
Visual inspection for overall health verification.

- *Maintenance manual.* The designer must indicate the correct maintenance procedure. These procedures must consider material properties and component functionality. The maintenance manual should also specify who is qualified to perform special maintenance actions.

Maintenance manual

Detected anomalies

Humidity	POSSIBLE CAUSES: Presence of surface aquifer, non-insulated foundations, presence of rising by capillarity, not high breathability of the plaster mortar EFFECTS: surface efflorescence, damp walls, formation of surface stains INTERVENTION CRITERIA: inspection by a qualified technician, waterproofing project and/or dehumidification
Infiltration	POSSIBLE CAUSES: Infiltrations from the roof, leaks of technological systems EFFECTS: formation of surface stains, wet walls INTERVENTION CRITERIA: inspection by a qualified technician, restoration of waterproofing, restoration of systems, restoration of the initial condition of the plaster
Cracking	POSSIBLE CAUSES: Foundational settlements, excessive deformations EFFECTS: visible cracking pattern, not verticality of piers INTERVENTION CRITERIA: inspection by a qualified technician, consolidation and filling of cracks, inhibition of possible causes (foundation consolidation)

- *Maintenance program.* A document composed of three subprograms:
 - o Performance subprogramme, which examines, by risk classes, the services provided during the life cycle of the structure. The designer must identify requirements and related performance for each part of the structure and each of its components.;
 - o Controls subprogramme: the designer must define a programme of controls and verifications with deadlines. In the controls subprogramme, the designer must indicate the extreme performance values: the test value and the minimum value.
 - o Interventions subprogramme: the designer must define a programme of potential interventions to restore parts of the structure to their initial condition.

Maintenance program				
Performance subprogram				
General	Object	Prestation required		Useful life (years)
Structures	CONSTRAIN mortar coating, reinforced and unreinforced masonry elements	Mechanical strength, durability and functionality		50
Controls subprogram				
General	Description	Control description		
		Visual inspection	Deeper	Instrumental
Structures	The surfaces of the elements and of the CONSTRAIN mortar coating must not have anomalies and/or in any case cracks, surface bubbles. In the presence of cracks or lesions or horizontal and vertical deformations foresee installation of analogue or digital meters or possible control of deformations with localised load test.	Every year	Quinquennial	If necessary
Maintenance subprogram				
Object	Intervention		Program	Extension
Masonry elements	Any structural restoration and sealing of any cracks and moisture penetrations with the use of chemicals that do not alter the chromatic characteristics of the elements.		If necessary	Degradation parts

4. INFORMATION FOR BUILDERS

4.1. How to read the drawings and technical documentation

Each material type is described with its geometrical and mechanical proprieties.

For example:

- **The GFRP (Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer) mesh and corner elements** (Fig. 4.1)

The mesh products have different configurations, usually indicated by a mesh dimension “n x m” (where n is the distance between weft wires and m is the distance between warp wires; typically, m = n), the linear density of fibres (where the number indicates the tex value), and the type of composite (e.g. resistant glass fibres and vinylester resin). For GFRP angular elements, the dimensions of the two sides and the angle must also be specified.

Fig. 4.1 GFRP mesh and GFRP angular mesh

- **GFRP connectors**

GFRP connectors are L-shaped preformed bars made of fibre-reinforced polymer (Fig. 4.2). They may have different lengths, depending on the thickness of the masonry elements or the type of reinforcement system (one side or two sides). For the GFRP connectors, the nominal dimensions (cross-section and length of the two sides) and the fibre density must be specified.

Fig. 4.2 GFRP connector

- ***Chemical anchors***

Vinylester resin is normally used. The exact commercial product needs to be specified.

- ***Inorganic matrix***

The type of mortar shall be defined by its compressive strength (after 28 days of curing on prismatic specimens) and the type of bonding agent (lime or cement). The total nominal thickness also needs to be specified.

- ***Steel diatoms and other devices***

Steel for diatoms, as well as washers and nuts, must guarantee the same durability as the GFRP elements. Therefore, it is mandatory to use weldable stainless steel. Normally, AISI 316 stainless steel is the recommended class for these elements.

An example of technical drawings is shown in Figs. 4.3–4.5. The material list shall indicate the type of mesh and mortar.

Fig. 4.3 An example of technical drawing: strengthening on both sides of the walls.

Fig. 4.4 An example of technical drawing: strengthening single leaf masonry on one side of the walls.

Fig. 4.5 An example of technical drawing: Strengthening double leaf wall with coating on one side.

4.2. Preliminary phases before the application of the system

Before the CRM system can be applied, a preliminary inspection is required, and precautions must be taken to prevent local collapse of the structure. During these initial operations, the builders, in collaboration with the construction manager, are responsible for verifying that the actual condition of the walls matches the project specifications. This includes checking the masonry in terms of geometry (type of blocks, thickness, presence of different layers, types of joints, etc.) and materials (constituent material and origin of bricks or stones, mortar joints, any plaster mortars, possible presence of diatones, etc.).

During the removal of existing plaster or other demolition works, no damage should occur that creates unsafe conditions. Any damage to the existing walls must be repaired. In the case of serious damage, it is recommended to use "indenting" (replacing masonry in the cracked area) to restore the mechanical properties of the masonry to their original state. For indenting, it is necessary to use elements (stone or bricks) and mortars with mechanical properties (strength and stiffness) similar to those of the existing materials, to recreate homogeneous masonry before applying the reinforcement. Significant differences in mechanical properties between the new indenting material and the existing masonry can result in ineffective stress distribution during earthquakes.

Another issue to identify after removing the plasters is the non-homogeneous stone masonry. The cohesion between elements must be adequate for the safe installation of the reinforcement.

4.3. Application phases and precautions

The procedure for installing the CRM system on both sides of the wall (Fig. 4.6) is as follows:

- **Phase 1** *Removal of the existing plaster from the wall*

After the existing plaster has been removed, wash the external surfaces with a high-pressure washer. Power washing should remove disintegrated and cohesion-free mortar to a depth of 10–15 mm. This will create space for new mortar within the masonry joints and improve adhesion. Washing should completely remove dust from the surface of the bricks. The washing must be carried out from the top to the bottom of the wall.

- **Phase 2** *Initial rendering*

Before rendering, the masonry must be wetted. The substrate should be saturated with water, but without surface drops. Under certain conditions, it may be necessary to apply a layer of plastering mortar. This depends on the condition of the wall surface and the performance characteristics (in both fresh and hardened state) of the mortar to be used. In such cases, apply a 5–10 mm thick layer of plastering mortar to cover the substrate. Comb the plastering mortar from the bottom up using a special notched trowel (10 mm). This creates a rough and irregular surface profile that ensures perfect cohesion for the next layer of plaster. It is recommended to apply the plastering mortar with the correct consistency to achieve adequate roughness. Wait at least 24 hours for the rough coating to cure before proceeding with the next steps.

- **Phase 3** *Drilling of holes in the wall for the installation of the L-shaped connectors*

Mark the positions for the connectors on the wall surface according to the design (number of connectors per square metre and expected average distance between them). Drill holes for transverse connectors using a rotary drill. Note that using percussion on very damaged walls can cause significant further damage; in such cases, drill by simple rotation.

When the system is applied to only one side of the masonry, the holes for installing the L-connectors, with a diameter of approximately 16 mm, must be drilled to a depth of at least two-thirds of the masonry thickness.

In contrast, when the system is applied to both sides of the masonry, the holes must accommodate the insertion of two connectors, one from each side of the wall: a "long" connector and a "short" connector, with lengths selected to ensure a minimum overlap of 15 cm. Drill a hole with a diameter of approximately 16 mm through the entire thickness of the masonry. Then, enlarge the diameter of the hole to approximately 24 mm on the side of the wall where the "short" connectors will be inserted, for a length slightly greater than that of the "short" connector. Clean the inside of the holes by removing dust from drilling with a jet of compressed air.

- **Phase 4** *Installation of artificial diatonas*

In the case of double or multiple-leaf masonry strengthened only on one side, install artificial diatonas as follows:

drill holes of the prescribed diameter (approximately 50 mm), almost entirely through the wall thickness (at least two-thirds). Clean the holes with compressed air, wet the holes, clean the bar, insert the stainless steel threaded bar with special centring elements. Mix the cement grout for at least 5 minutes, using the quantity of water specified in the product's technical data sheet. Add 80% of the total water to the initial mix, then the powder product, followed by the remaining water until the required total is reached. Inject the cement grout with a machine. Check the implementation. Cure after final wetting of the support (maturation time of at least 28 days).

- **Phase 5** *Installation of the bars for anchoring to foundation, floors, walls*

Drill holes for the bars securing the reinforced coating system to foundations, floors, or other structural elements. Use a rotary drill for this operation. The hole diameter must be equal to the nominal diameter of the bar plus 2 mm. The hole depth must ensure an anchoring length of at least 40 times the bar diameter, unless adequate tests demonstrate that a fixed connection with the foundation can be achieved at a lesser depth, which may also depend on the mechanical properties of the anchoring resins. The spacing between bars should be between 0.33 m and 0.40 m; this is a general guideline, but the actual spacing depends on the type of anchoring elements and the mechanical resistance of the GFRP meshes and mortar. The resisting cross-section of the bars is determined during the structural verification phase.

Clean dust from the holes using a jet of compressed air. Inject resin into the holes and install the stainless-steel threaded bars.

- **Phase 6** *Installation of mesh*

Position the mesh on the masonry surfaces. The overlap between two sheets of mesh must exceed 20 cm, and a series of connectors shall be applied at the overlap to improve it. Only if the system has a specific test report certifying a different overlap size may a value of less than 20 cm be used. The overlap of the mesh with the anchoring bars is approximately 50 diameters for straight bars.

At the corners of a building, where the bending angle is 90°, an angular mesh element can be used, as the GFRP mesh is brittle and cannot be bent. In this case, a prefabricated element with the correct 90° bend should be used. The overlap between the angular element and the mesh should be the same as between two sheets of mesh, i.e., greater than 20 cm. A series of connectors should be applied at the overlap to improve the connection.

- **Phase 7** *Installation of the L-shaped connectors*

For the strengthening system applied on one side, ensure the resin injection reaches the deepest part of the hole. Place a centred small square mesh patch (for stress distribution) over the hole, above the mesh, and insert the connector to the maximum depth. Correct filling of the cavity is confirmed when, upon inserting the connector, a small amount of resin flows from the hole.

For the strengthening system applied to both sides of the wall, inject resin into the narrow portion of the holes. Place a centred small square mesh patch (for stress distribution) over the hole, then insert the “long” connector above the mesh. Next, inject resin into the enlarged portion of the holes. The injection must fill the entire enlarged portion and ensure at least partial penetration into the narrow part. Place a centred small mesh patch over the hole, then insert the “short” connector above the mesh.

Wait until the injection resin has fully hardened before applying the mortar coating.

- **Phase 8 Application of mortar coating**

If dust or debris is produced during the previous phases, it must be cleaned. Depending on the type of mortar and the desired thickness, the mortar coating can be applied in a single layer (normally for thicknesses up to 30 mm) or in two or more successive layers. During application, ensure the mesh is correctly positioned in the middle of the thickness. The plaster must be wet cured by avoiding intense sun exposure or ventilation and by wetting it at least twice a day for 7 days, starting 24–48 hours after laying. The finishing coating can be applied after at least 10 days. Paint or coloured coatings may be applied only after the plaster has matured and, in any case, not before 28 days from laying.

Fig. 4.6 Main phases in the installation of CONSTRAN strengthening on two sides: a) remove existing plastering and clear joints up to a depth 10-15 mm, b) drill holes and install mesh and connectors, c) application of the mortar coating.

4.4. Specific precautions in application of mortar and curing phases

The mortar must be installed in layers. This sequence is necessary to prevent the water in the mortar from being absorbed by the masonry.

- *Rough coating* (Fig. 4.7a): The first layer is applied by hand using a standard trowel, projecting the mortar film without spreading it on the substrate. This application is recommended for small surfaces and when applying mortar is difficult.
- *Mortar coating* (Fig. 4.7b): For application of the coating, each layer of mortar must have a very fluid consistency to ensure complete coverage of the substrate. The mortar layers can be applied using suitable pumps for traditional mortars or with a trowel, following standard procedures for plasters and masonry mortars. The minimum thickness of each layer is 10 mm, and the maximum is 30 mm. Layers can be applied a few hours apart, ensuring that the indicated thicknesses are not exceeded during installation. Shortly before the end of setting, the product must be properly trowelled to prevent cracks caused by initial water evaporation. After the product has set, maintain the application by spraying a water mist on the surface at regular intervals during the first 24 to 48 hours.
- *Finishing layer*: A finishing layer can be applied to improve the aesthetic appearance and protect the reinforcement. The products, applied by hand or machine, can then be smoothed with a steel trowel for a smooth finish or roughened using a sponge or plastic trowel. Finally, breathable paints or coatings can be applied to ensure the breathability of the lime mortar. Paint should be applied only after the mortars have cured. If environmental conditions are aggressive, resistant mortars and compatible protective finishes should be used.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4.7 Application of rough coating (a) and mortar coating (b)

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PRO-SIS Report 2.4 - ANNEX A - Examples of price analyses

Italian price analysis

PA.01 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT – GALVANIZED STEEL REINFORCED CEMENT MORTAR					
<p>Two-sided structural reinforcement of masonry or concrete walls using a cement plaster with a variable thickness of 30 mm to 70 mm, combined with galvanized welded wire mesh $\varnothing 6$, 20x20 cm, including transverse passing-through connections $6\varnothing 6/m^2$ in $\varnothing 10$ holes.</p> <p>INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of existing plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the wall surface; drilling of holes at a rate no less than 6/m²; insertion of the transverse connections described above; application of the concrete layer, and all other operations necessary to deliver the finished work in accordance with the recognized standards of workmanship</p> <p>EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at wall intersections with horizontal and vertical structural elements Scaffolding, platforms, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the works, as well as any protective coverings installed against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.</p> <p>Application on both sides of the wall and for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. The price is applied per square meter of wall.</p>			<p>Masonry Concrete steel mesh steel bars</p>		
CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	CEMENT MORTAR FOR WALL CONSOLIDATION, average thickness of 5 cm.	m ²	2.00	26.03 €	52.06 €
Materials	STEEL type B450C controlled – Electro-welded mesh $\varnothing 6$, 20x20 cm	Kg.	4.880	1.96 €	9.56 €
Materials	STEEL type B450C controlled - Ribbed steel bars for continuous transverse connections, $6\varnothing 6/m^2$, L= 0.8 m	Kg.	1.065	2.00 €	2.13 €
Materials	Surcharge for hot-dip galvanizing of steel elements	Kg.	5.945	2.00 €	11.89 €
Materials	Flowable premixed mortar, type EMACO S or equivalent	Kg.	0.855	2.60 €	2.22 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	1.16	3.50 €	4.06 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	1.00	1.25 €	1.25 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	1.16	27.20 €	31.55 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	1.10	30.28 €	33.31 €
					148.04 €
	Transport expenses	2%			2.96 €
	General expenses	15%			22.65 €
	Company profit	10%			17.36 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m² 191.01 €

PA.01.1 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT – GALVANIZED STEEL REINFORCED CEMENT MORTAR
Surcharge for connection with foundations and across floors

Two-sided structural reinforcement - galvanized steel reinforced cement mortar coating.
 Surcharge for the execution of the connection of the reinforced coating with the foundation and across floors, by using galvanized ribbed steel bars Ø8, B450C, applied at a rate of 4/m at both wall sides. The bar is bonded to the masonry at the through hole and embedded within the coating of the reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with flowable premixed mortar type EMACO S, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on both sides of the wall.
 The price is applied per meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type B450C controlled - Ribbed steel bars, L= 0.9 m, 4/m	Kg.	2.844	2.00 €	5.69 €
Materials	Surcharge for hot-dip galvanizing of steel elements	Kg.	2.844	2.00 €	5.69 €
Materials	Flowable premixed mortar, type EMACO S or equivalent	Kg.	1.62	2.60 €	4.21 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.06	3.50 €	0.21 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.06	27.20 €	1.63 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.06	30.28 €	1.82 €
					19.25 €
	Transport expenses	2%			0.38 €
	General expenses	15%			2.94 €
	Company profit	10%			2.26 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m	24.83 €

PA.01bis STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT – UNPROTECTED STEEL REINFORCED CEMENT MORTAR

Two-sided structural reinforcement of masonry or concrete walls using a cement plaster with a variable thickness of 30 mm to 70 mm, combined with welded wire mesh $\varnothing 6$, 20x20 cm, including transverse passing-through connections $6\varnothing 6/m^2$ in $\varnothing 10$ holes.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of existing plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the wall surface; drilling of holes at a rate no less than 6/m²; insertion of the transverse connections described above, at a rate of not less than 6/m²; application of the concrete layer, and all other operations necessary to deliver the finished work in accordance with the recognized standards of workmanship

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at wall intersections with horizontal and vertical structural elements Scaffolding, platforms, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the works, as well as any protective coverings installed against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on both sides of the wall and for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm.

The price is applied per square meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	CEMENT MORTAR FOR WALL CONSOLIDATION, average thickness of 5 cm.	m ²	2.00	26.03 €	52.06 €
Materials	STEEL type B450C controlled – Electro-welded mesh $\varnothing 6$, 20x20 cm	Kg.	4.880	1.96 €	9.56 €
Materials	STEEL type B450C controlled - Ribbed steel bars for continuous transverse connections, $6\varnothing 6/m^2$, L= 0.8 m	Kg.	1.065	2.00 €	2.13 €
Materials	Flowable premixed mortar, type EMACO S or equivalent	Kg.	0.855	2.60 €	2.22 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	1.16	3.50 €	4.06 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	1.00	1.25 €	1.25 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	1.16	27.20 €	31.55 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	1.10	30.28 €	33.31 €
					136.15 €
	Transport expenses	2%			2.72 €
	General expenses	15%			20.83 €
	Company profit	10%			15.97 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m² 175.67 €

PA.01.1bis STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT – UNPROTECTED STEEL REINFORCED CEMENT MORTAR
Surcharge for connection with foundations and across floors

Two-sided structural reinforcement - unprotected steel reinforced cement mortar coating.
 Surcharge for the execution of the connection of the reinforced coating with the foundation and across floors, by using unprotected steel ribbed bars Ø8, B450C, applied at a rate of 4/m at both wall sides. The bar is bonded to the masonry at the through hole and embedded within the coating of the reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with flowable premixed mortar type EMACO S, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on both sides of the wall.
 The price is applied per meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type B450C controlled - Ribbed steel bars, L= 0.9 m, 4/m	Kg.	2.844	2.00 €	5.69 €
Materials	Flowable premixed mortar, type EMACO S or equivalent	Kg.	1.620	2.60 €	4.21 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.06	3.50 €	0.21 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.06	27.20 €	1.63 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.06	30.28 €	1.82 €
					13.56 €
	Transport expenses	2%			0.27 €
	General expenses	15%			2.07 €
	Company profit	10%			1.59 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m	17.49 €

PA.02

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER
One-sided for single-leaf masonry

One-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:

- Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBESH66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%.

- GFRP "L" shape composite material connectors FBCONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for non-through transversal connection on a $\varnothing 12$ mm diameter hole, at a rate of 6/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments < 3%.

- Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection;

- Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

The system is completed with premixed lime-based plaster mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on one face of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm.

Price applies per square meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Premixed lime and cement mortar for structural applications - M10	Kg.	40.00	0.45 €	18.00 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBESH 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBCON connectors (n° 6/m ²); GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices (n° 6/m ²); Vinylester chemical anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	m ²	1.00	46.78 €	46.78 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.58	3.50 €	2.03 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	1.00	1.10 €	1.10 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.58	27.20 €	15.78 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.55	30.28 €	16.65 €
					100.34 €
	Transport expenses	2%			2.01 €
	General expenses	15%			15.35 €
	Company profit	10%			11.77 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m² 129.47 €

PA.02.1 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER and ARTIFICIAL DIATONES - One-sided for multiple-leaf masonry

One-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:

- Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBESH66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%.

- GFRP "L" shape composite material connectors FBCONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for non-through transversal connection on a $\varnothing 12$ mm diameter hole, at a rate of 4/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments <3%.

- Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection;

- Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

These components are combined with artificial diatons at a rate of 2/m², consisting of a core of flowable premixed mortar type EMACO S, or equivalent, installed in non-through transverse holes with a diameter of 50 mm, into which a stainless steel M16 bar is embedded, fitted with a 50 mm diameter perforated metal washer, 4 mm thick.

The system is completed with premixed lime-based plaster mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish.

Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the GFRP transverse connections, at a rate no less than 4/m², and of artificial ties, in a quantity not less than 2/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on one face of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Premixed lime and cement mortar for structural applications - M10	Kg.	40.00	0.45 €	18.00 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBESH 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBCON connectors (n° 4/m ²); GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices (n° 4/m ²); Vinylester chemical anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	m ²	1.00	41.68 €	41.68 €
Materials	STAINLESS STEEL type AISI 316 - M16 bars, length =60 cm (2/m ²)	Kg.	1.596	12.00 €	19.15 €
Materials	STAINLESS STEEL type AISI 316 - M16 bolt with washer, diameter 150 mm, thickness 4 mm (2/m ²)	Kg.	1.200	21.75 €	26.10 €
Materials	Flowable premixed mortar type EMACO S or equivalent	Kg.	0.798	0.80 €	0.64 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.68	3.50 €	2.38 €
Rentals	Bare rental of water-cooled rotary percussion core drilling equipment	h	0.50	19.50 €	9.75 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	1.00	1.10 €	1.10 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.68	27.20 €	18.50 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.65	30.28 €	19.68 €
					156.98 €
	Transport expenses	2%			3.14 €
	General expenses	15%			24.02 €
	Company profit	10%			18.41 €
	APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m² 202.55 €

PA.03 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER - Two-sided

Two-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:

- Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBESH66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%.

- GFRP "L" shape composite material connectors FBCONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for transversal passing-through connection on a $\varnothing 24$ mm diameter hole, at a rate of 6/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments < 3%.

- Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection;

- Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

The system is completed with premixed lime-based plaster mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on both faces of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Premixed lime and cement mortar for structural applications - M10	Kg.	80.00	0.45 €	36.00 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBESH 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBCON connectors (n° 6/m ²); GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices(n° 6/m ²); Vinylester chemical anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	m ²	2.00	46.78 €	93.56 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	1.16	3.50 €	4.06 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	2.00	1.10 €	2.20 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	1.16	27.20 €	31.55 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	1.10	30.28 €	33.31 €
					200.68 €
	Transport expenses	2%			4.01 €
	General expenses	15%			30.70 €
	Company profit	10%			23.54 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m² 258.94 €

PA.03.1 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER - Two-sided with steel ties

Two-sided structural reinforcement of concrete walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, metal connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:

- Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBMesh66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%.
- Stainless steel connectors for transverse connections, at a rate of 6/m², consisting of M8 threaded rods passing through $\varnothing 12$ holes, with 50x1.5 mm washer and nut, grade 8.8, at both wall sides.
- Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection;
- Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

The system is completed with hydraulic cement mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 5 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 25 MPa.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on both faces of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	CEMENT MORTAR FOR WALL CONSOLIDATION, average thickness of 5 cm.	m ²	2.00	26.03 €	52.06 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBMesh 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices(n° 6/m ²)	m ²	2.00	23.34 €	46.68 €
Materials	Stainless steel type AISI 316 - M8 bars, average length 50 cm (n° 6/m ²)	Kg.	1.183	17.79 €	21.04 €
Materials	Stainless steel type AISI 316 - M8 bolt with 50 mm diameter, 1.5 mm thick washer (n° 6/m ²)	Kg.	0.555	17.79 €	9.86 €
Materials	Chemical vinylester anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	Kg.	0.339	23.00 €	7.80 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	1.16	3.50 €	4.06 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	2.00	1.10 €	2.20 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	1.16	27.20 €	31.55 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	1.10	30.28 €	33.31 €
					208.57 €
	Transport expenses	2%			4.17 €
	General expenses	15%			31.91 €
	Company profit	10%			24.46 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m² 269.11 €

PA.04

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER

Surcharge for corner connection

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of connections at masonry corners, by using the corner element FBANG66X66T96 by Fibrenet, or equivalent, featuring CE marking, preformed with a 90° bend, consisting of a square mesh with 66x66 mm openings, manufactured with Alkali-Resistant glass roving and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with nominal strand diameter exceeding 3 mm and a width of 33 cm per side. Tensile strength of the composite ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of the individual bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile modulus of elasticity $\geq 25,000$ N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of the individual bar ≥ 4.14 kN, average elongation at failure 1.78%, characteristic node tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and modulus of elasticity in humid, alkaline, and saline environments $< 8\%$.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: All that is necessary to deliver the finished work in accordance with best practice.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment required for the execution of the work, any protective coverings installed against atmospheric agents, and anything else not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Corner element in GFRP FBANG66X66T96AR, 33 cm width per side	m	1.00	17.75 €	17.75 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.10	27.20 €	2.72 €
					20.47 €
	Transport expenses	2%			0.41 €
	General expenses	15%			3.13 €
	Company profit	10%			2.40 €
	APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m 26.41 €

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER

PA.05 Surcharge for connection with foundations and across floors, and across symmetric "T-shape" wall intersections

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of the connections of the CRM system with the foundation and across floors, as well as across symmetric "T-shape" wall intersections, by using M8 stainless steel threaded bars in Ø12 diameter holes, and thermosetting vinylesterepoxy resin, applied at a rate of 3/m. The bar is bonded to the masonry at the through hole and embedded within the CRM structural reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with vinylester-epoxy resin FIXA VINYL 15 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 rods average length = 90 cm (3/m)	Kg.	1.065	17.79 €	18.94 €
Materials	Chemical Vinylester Anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	Kg.	0.203	23.00 €	4.68 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.06	3.50 €	0.21 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.06	27.20 €	1.63 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.06	30.28 €	1.82 €
					27.28 €
	Transport expenses	2%			0.55 €
	General expenses	15%			4.17 €
	Company profit	10%			3.20 €
	APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m 35.20 €

PA.06 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER
Surcharge for connection across unsymmetric "T-shape" wall intersections

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of wall T-junctions using M8 stainless steel threaded bars embedded in a passing-through hole of diameter Ø12, M8 bolt, 50x1.5 washer, load-distribution device made of preformed mesh in glass fiber reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, calculated at 3/m. The bar is anchored to the masonry at the hole and embedded in the CRM structural reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with vinylester-epoxy resin FIXA VINYL 15 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 rods average length = 80 cm (3/m)	Kg.	1.170	17.79 €	20.81 €
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 bolt + washer diameter 50 mm thickness 1.5 mm (3/ml)	Kg.	0.069	17.79 €	1.23 €
Materials	GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices (3/m);	m ²	0.27	17.75 €	4.79 €
Materials	Chemical Vinylester Anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	Kg.	0.170	23.00 €	3.90 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.10	3.50 €	0.35 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.10	27.20 €	2.72 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.10	30.28 €	3.03 €
					36.83 €
	Transport expenses	2%			0.74 €
	General expenses	15%			5.64 €
	Company profit	10%			4.32 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m 47.52 €

PA.02 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER					
One-sided for single-leaf masonry					
<p>One-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>Preformed mesh</u> made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBESH66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%. - GFRP "L" shape composite material <u>connectors</u> FBCONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for non-through transversal connection on a $\varnothing 12$ mm diameter hole, at a rate of 6/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments < 3%. - <u>Load distribution devices</u> made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection; - <u>Chemical anchor</u> for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent. <p>The system is completed with premixed lime-based <u>plaster mortar</u> for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.</p> <p>INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.</p> <p>EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.</p> <p>Application on one face of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.</p>					
CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Premixed lime and cement mortar for structural applications - M10	Kg.	40.00	0.45 €	18.00 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBESH 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBCON connectors (n° 6/m ²); GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices (n° 6/m ²); Vinylester chemical anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	m ²	1.00	46.78 €	46.78 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.58	2.47 €	1.43 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	1.00	0.82 €	0.82 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.58	22.51 €	13.06 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.55	24.36 €	13.40 €
Transport	Transport expenses				2.18 €
					95.66 €
	General expenses	15%			14.35 €
	Company profit	10%			9.57 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m² 119.58 €

PA.03 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT - CRM REINFORCED PLASTER - Two-sided

Two-sided structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria), composed of mesh, connectors, and distribution devices made of GFRP (Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer) composite and vinylester chemical anchor, with the following characteristics:

- Preformed mesh made of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBMesh66x66T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, for structural reinforcement. Alkali-Resistant mesh, with monolithic square mesh size 66x66 mm, produced by using Textrusion technology, composed of glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, woven with multiple twist warp and flat weft inserted between warp fibers, nominal strand diameter > 3 mm, with 15 bars/meter/side, composite characteristic tensile strength ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of a single bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile Elastic Modulus ≥ 25000 N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of a single bar ≥ 4.23 kN, average elongation at break 1.78%, characteristic knot tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and elastic modulus under humid, alkaline, and saline conditions < 8%.

- GFRP "L" shape composite material connectors FBCONL by Fibre Net, or equivalent, for transversal passing-through connection on a $\varnothing 24$ mm diameter hole, at a rate of 6/m², provided with CE marking, composed of Alkaline-Resistant glass fiber and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with a cross-section of 10 x 7 mm, composite elastic modulus ≥ 26500 N/mm² and characteristic tensile strength ≥ 26.6 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and Elastic Modulus due to humid, alkaline, and saline environments < 3%.

- Load distribution devices made of preformed mesh of fiber-reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, provided with CE marking, for each connection;

- Chemical anchor for structural anchoring FIXA VINYL15-400 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

The system is completed with premixed lime-based plaster mortar for structural applications, with a minimum thickness of 3 cm and a trowel finish. Compressive strength at 28 days ≥ 10 MPa, flexural strength ≥ 1.2 MPa, compressive elastic modulus 10 ± 2 GPa, adhesion to masonry substrate ≥ 0.5 MPa.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Removal of plaster; thorough washing and cleaning of the masonry surface; execution of perforations; insertion of the aforementioned transverse connections, at a rate no less than 6/m², and application of mortar. Also included is everything necessary to deliver the work completed in accordance with the best professional practices.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Reinforcement at junctions between masonry and horizontal or vertical structural elements; scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for executing the works, as well as any coverings installed to protect against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

Application on both faces of the wall, for wall thicknesses up to 60 cm. Price applies per square meter of wall.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Premixed lime and cement mortar for structural applications - M10	Kg.	80.00	0.45 €	36.00 €
Materials	RI-STRUTTURA system composed of: GFRP FBMesh 66X66T96AR mesh, complete with overlaps; GFRP FBCON connectors (n° 6/m ²); GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices(n° 6/m ²); Vinylester chemical anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	m ²	2.00	46.78 €	93.56 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	1.16	2.47 €	2.87 €
Rentals	Bare rental of a single-phase plastering machine for traditional or premixed plaster.	m ²	2.00	0.82 €	1.63 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	1.16	22.51 €	26.11 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	1.10	24.36 €	26.80 €
Transport	Transport expenses				1.91 €
					188.87 €
	General expenses	15%			28.33 €
	Company profit	10%			18.89 €
	APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m² 236.09 €

PA.04

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER

Surcharge for corner connection

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of connections at masonry corners, by using the corner element FBANG66X66T96 by FibreNet, or equivalent, featuring CE marking, preformed with a 90° bend, consisting of a square mesh with 66x66 mm openings, manufactured with Alkali-Resistant glass roving and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, with nominal strand diameter exceeding 3 mm and a width of 33 cm per side. Tensile strength of the composite ≥ 376 MPa, nominal cross-sectional area of the individual bar ≥ 8.9 mm², equivalent tensile modulus of elasticity $\geq 25,000$ N/mm², characteristic tensile strength of the individual bar ≥ 4.14 kN, average elongation at failure 1.78%, characteristic node tear resistance ≥ 0.25 kN. Reduction in tensile strength and modulus of elasticity in humid, alkaline, and saline environments $< 8\%$.

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: All that is necessary to deliver the finished work in accordance with best practice.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment required for the execution of the work, any protective coverings installed against atmospheric agents, and anything else not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	Corner element in GFRP FBANG66X66T96AR, 33 cm width per side	m	1.00	17.75 €	17.75 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.10	22.51 €	2.25 €
					20.00 €
	General expenses	15%			3.00 €
	Company profit	10%			2.00 €
	APPLIED UNIT PRICE				m 25.00 €

STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER

PA.05 Surcharge for connection with foundations and across floors, and across symmetric "T-shape" wall intersections

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of the connections of the CRM system with the foundation and across floors, as well as across symmetric "T-shape" wall intersections, by using M8 stainless steel threaded bars in Ø12 diameter holes, and thermosetting vinylesterepoxy resin, applied at a rate of 3/m. The bar is bonded to the masonry at the through hole and embedded within the CRM structural reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with vinylester-epoxy resin FIXA VINYL 15 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents., and any other items not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 rods average length = 90 cm (3/m)	Kg.	1.065	13.34 €	14.21 €
Materials	Chemical Vinylester Anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	Kg.	0.203	23.00 €	4.68 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.06	2.47 €	0.15 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.06	22.51 €	1.35 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.06	24.37 €	1.46 €
					21.85 €
	General expenses	15%			3.28 €
	Company profit	10%			2.18 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m 27.31 €

PA.06 STRUCTURAL REINFORCEMENT- CRM REINFORCED PLASTER
Surcharge for connection across unsymmetric "T-shape" wall intersections

Structural reinforcement of single-leaf masonry walls using the CRM - Composite Reinforced Mortar - System for strengthening masonry walls called "RI-STRUTTURA" by Fibre Net, or equivalent, certified with EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) for the declaration of contribution to CAM (Minimum Environmental Criteria).

Surcharge for the execution of wall T-junctions using M8 stainless steel threaded bars embedded in a passing-through hole of diameter Ø12, M8 bolt, 50x1.5 washer, load-distribution device made of preformed mesh in glass fiber reinforced composite material GFRP FBFAZ33X33T96AR by Fibre Net, or equivalent, with CE marking, and thermosetting vinylester-epoxy resin, calculated at 3/m. The bar is anchored to the masonry at the hole and embedded in the CRM structural reinforcement system (minimum anchorage length 50Ø).

INCLUDED IN THE PRICE: Drilling of holes of appropriate diameter and length, cleaning of holes from debris and dust, and bonding with vinylester-epoxy resin FIXA VINYL 15 by Fibre Net, or equivalent.

EXCLUDED FROM THE PRICE: Scaffolding, staging, and/or equipment necessary for the execution of the work, as well as any coverings installed for protection against atmospheric agents, and any other items not specified.

The price applies per linear meter.

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	UNIT	QUANTITY	PRICE	TOTAL
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 rods average length = 80 cm (3/m)	Kg.	1.170	13.34 €	15.61 €
Materials	STEEL type STAINLESS AISI 316 - M8 bolt + washer diameter 50 mm thickness 1.5 mm (3/ml)	Kg.	0.069	13.34 €	0.93 €
Materials	GFRP FBFAZZ33X33T96AR load distribution devices (3/m);	m ²	0.27	17.75 €	4.79 €
Materials	Chemical Vinylester Anchor INTEGRA FIXA VINYL15-400	Kg.	0.170	23.00 €	3.90 €
Rentals	Bare rental of petrol-driven air compressors with a capacity of 5000 l/min, including hole cleaning	h	0.10	2.47 €	0.25 €
Labors	Worker, 1st level	h	0.10	22.51 €	2.25 €
Labors	Worker, 2nd level	h	0.10	24.37 €	2.44 €
					30.16 €
	General expenses	15%			4.52 €
	Company profit	10%			3.02 €
APPLIED UNIT PRICE					m 37.70 €